

1 Light-regulated Gene Expression in Bacteria: 2 Fundamentals, Advances, and Perspectives

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9 Abstract

10 Numerous photoreceptors and genetic circuits emerged over the past two decades and now enable the light-
11 dependent, i.e. optogenetic, regulation of gene expression in bacteria. Prompted by light cues in the near-
12 ultraviolet to near-infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum, gene expression can be up- or
13 downregulated stringently, reversibly, non-invasively, and with precision in space and time. Here, we survey
14 the underlying principles, available options, and prominent examples of optogenetically regulated gene
15 expression in bacteria. While transcription initiation and elongation remain most important for optogenetic
16 intervention, other processes, e.g., translation and downstream events, were also rendered light-dependent.
17 The optogenetic control of bacterial expression predominantly employs but three fundamental strategies:
18 light-sensitive two-component systems, oligomerization reactions, and second-messenger signaling. Certain
19 optogenetic circuits moved beyond the proof-of-principle and stood the test of practice. They enable
20 unprecedented applications in three major areas. First, light-dependent expression underpins novel concepts
21 and strategies for enhanced yields in microbial production processes. Second, light-responsive bacteria can
22 be optogenetically stimulated while residing within the bodies of animals, thus prompting the secretion of
23 compounds that grant health benefits to the animal host. Third, optogenetics allows the generation of
24 precisely structured, novel biomaterials. These applications jointly testify to the maturity of the optogenetic
25 approach and serve as blueprints bound to inspire and template innovative use cases of light-regulated gene
26 expression in bacteria. Researchers pursuing these lines can choose from an ever-growing, versatile, and
27 efficient toolkit of optogenetic circuits.

28 Keywords

29 biotechnology; gene expression; optogenetics; sensory photoreceptor; signal transduction; synthetic biology

30 Introduction

31 Light-dependent adaptations of organismal development, behavior, and physiology abound in nature. Well-
32 known examples include vision, photomorphogenesis, phototropism, and phototaxis across diverse
33 organisms (Briggs, 2014; Butler et al., 1959; Engelmann, 1883). Although phenomenologically known early
34 on, many of the mechanistic details of light sensation long awaited elucidation until the molecular
35 identification of the underlying signal circuits. At the molecular stage, light is perceived by sensory
36 photoreceptor proteins which are sensitive to different bands of the near-ultraviolet (near-UV) to near-
37 infrared (NIR) region of the electromagnetic spectrum. Sensory photoreceptors translate photon absorption
38 by their chromophore into changes of their biological activity, for instance enzymatic activity or interaction
39 with other biomacromolecules (Fig. 1A). The molecular identification of photoreceptors and an
40 understanding of their inner workings, if often only partial, allowed their deployment in heterologous
41 organisms to modulate by light cellular state and processes, a discipline now known as optogenetics
42 (Deisseroth et al., 2006). Swiftly following their seminal description as light-gated cation-conducting channels
43 (Nagel et al., 2002, 2003), channelrhodopsins from unicellular algae served to control by light the ion gradient
44 across the plasma membrane and action potentials in mammalian cells (Boyden et al., 2005; Zhang et al.,
45 2007). Particular advantages of this and other optogenetic interventions are the genetic encoding, precise
46 spatiotemporal control, reversibility, and non-invasiveness.

47 By establishing the principal feasibility of optogenetics, these pioneering applications already hinted
48 at a much greater versatility and wider scope of the fundamental approach: evidently, optogenetics is not
49 restricted to neurobiology nor to mammalian cells alone. For one, certain other photoreceptors occurring in
50 nature were of immediate optogenetic utility without any or much modification, arguably best exemplified
51 by the photoactivated adenylyl cyclases from *Euglena gracilis* and *Beggiatoa* sp., respectively (Iseki et al.,
52 2002; Ryu et al., 2010; Schröder-Lang et al., 2007; Stierl et al., 2011). For another, artificial photoreceptors
53 with customized light response were engineered and unlocked additional cellular processes for optogenetics
54 (Levskaya et al., 2005; Möglich et al., 2009; Shimizu-Sato et al., 2002; Strickland et al., 2008; Wu et al., 2009).
55 The latter strategy was to large degree enabled by the discovery of the flavin-binding, blue-light-responsive
56 cryptochrome, LOV (light-oxygen-voltage), and BLUF (sensors of blue light using flavin adenine dinucleotide)
57 photoreceptor classes (Ahmad and Cashmore, 1993; Christie et al., 1998; Gomelsky and Klug, 2002; Iseki et
58 al., 2002). Of key importance and in common with plant and bacterial phytochromes (Butler et al., 1959;
59 Hughes et al., 1997), the LOV and BLUF photoreceptor classes exhibit decidedly modular architecture. In
60 contrast to rhodopsins which are frequently functional as single all-helical transmembrane domains
61 (Rozenberg et al., 2021), in the modular receptors photosensor and effector entities are precisely delineated
62 and can be physically separated. The abundance of naturally occurring, modular (photo)receptors provided
63 blueprints for the construction of artificial photoreceptors via recombination of photosensor and effector

64 modules. As a particularly versatile manifestation of this strategy, light-regulated association and dissociation
65 reactions, undergone by many photoreceptors, served to subject manifold target effectors to light control.
66 Owing to the collective efforts of many scientists, a broad set of optogenetic tools is now at hand to govern
67 by light various aspects of cellular physiology and signaling, in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes (Govorunova
68 et al., 2022; Losi et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2021).

69 Notwithstanding the sheer diversity of optogenetic modalities realized to date, the regulation of gene
70 expression by light remains particularly widespread and versatile (Fig. 1A). Although slow in response
71 compared to other optogenetic strategies, light-regulated gene expression provides a general and highly
72 adaptable means of modifying diverse traits of target cells and organisms. Moreover, changes in gene
73 expression elicited by light are generally long-lasting and yield persistent effects, rather than the transient
74 cellular responses of many other optogenetic approaches. Assuming a desired application does not demand
75 utmost temporal resolution as frequently needed in cell biology and the neurosciences, light-regulated gene
76 expression hence often appears as the method of choice for optogenetic control. As reviewed elsewhere
77 (Losi et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2021), several setups for the light-dependent regulation of eukaryotic gene
78 expression emerged in the two decades after the first such system was established for yeast (Shimizu-Sato
79 et al., 2002). Here, we review the current state and recent developments of light-regulated gene expression
80 in prokaryotes. Since the arrival of the initial optogenetic setups for gene expression in bacteria (Levskaya et
81 al., 2005; Möglich et al., 2009; Ohlendorf et al., 2012; Tabor et al., 2011), many more systems were advanced
82 (Baumschlager and Khammash, 2021; Fischer et al., 2022; Hoffman et al., 2022; Lindner and Diepold, 2022;
83 Mazraeh and Di Ventura, 2022; Reshetnikov et al., 2022). In this article, we first recapitulate fundamental
84 aspects of photoreceptors and optogenetics as they pertain to light-regulated gene expression. Next, we
85 move on to the principal strategies currently available for controlling bacterial expression by light. Last, we
86 consider the increasingly numerous and diverse applications in synthetic biology and biotechnology that
87 capitalize on the exquisite spatiotemporal resolution, noninvasiveness, and reversibility afforded by
88 optogenetics.

89 Sensory photoreceptors for bacterial optogenetics

90 Based on chromophore type and the photochemical reactions elicited by light absorption, the sensory
91 photoreceptors identified to date can be grouped into around ten distinct families (Ziegler and Möglich,
92 2015). Together, these families cover the entire near-ultraviolet to near-infrared section of the
93 electromagnetic spectrum (Fig. 1B). Given that the photochemistry, structure, and signaling mechanisms of
94 sensory photoreceptors have been reviewed elsewhere, e.g., (Losi et al., 2018; Möglich, 2019; Rozenberg et
95 al., 2021; Tang et al., 2021), the current focus is on salient aspects as they pertain to applications in bacteria.
96 Sensory photoreceptors generally traverse between their dark-adapted (or, resting) and light-adapted (or,

97 signaling) states. Light absorption by the chromophore within the dark-adapted photoreceptor triggers a
98 series of photochemical events, collectively known as the photocycle, and leads to population of the
99 metastable light-adapted state. The initial reaction triggered by photon absorption is generally fast to ensure
100 high quantum efficiency for signal transduction. Several intermediates may occur en route to the signaling
101 state but are short-lived. Given that the lifetime of these intermediates is generally much shorter than the
102 relevant timescales of many cellular signal responses and gene expression in particular, for the present
103 context we only consider the dark-adapted and light-adapted states. With notable exceptions (Ortiz-
104 Guerrero et al., 2011), sensory photoreceptors generally operate reversibly, and the light-adapted state
105 passively, i.e. thermally, reverts to the resting state in the so-called dark-recovery reaction. Certain
106 photoreceptor classes, e.g., bacterial phytochromes and cyanobacteriochromes, are photochromic in that
107 the signaling state can be actively returned to the dark-adapted state via absorption of a second photon,
108 usually of different wavelength than the initial photon absorption. The photocycle of photochromic receptors
109 can thus be deliberately abridged to potentially enhance the spatial and temporal precision of optogenetic
110 applications (Ziegler and Möglich, 2015). We note that photochromic reversion to the dark-adapted state
111 also applies to LOV receptors (Losi et al., 2013). Arguably owing to the the low efficiency of this process and
112 the requirement for UV radiation, photochromicity in LOV receptors has not been leveraged for bacterial
113 optogenetics to date.

114 All in all, the strategies for the optogenetic regulation of bacterial expression predominantly harness
115 LOV receptors (Christie et al., 1998; Losi et al., 2018), bacterial phytochromes (BphP) (Chernov et al., 2017;
116 Tang et al., 2021), and cyanobacteriochromes (CBCR) (Rockwell and Lagarias, 2010). By contrast, plant
117 phytochromes and cryptochromes (Kennedy et al., 2010; Shimizu-Sato et al., 2002; Tang et al., 2021),
118 frequently used for optogenetically regulating gene expression in mammalian hosts, have seen scant, if any,
119 use in prokaryotes, arguably due to the size of these receptors and difficulties of functionally expressing them
120 in bacteria. LOV receptors bind flavin-nucleotide cofactors, mostly flavin mononucleotide, to absorb blue
121 light (ca. 420-490 nm) (Christie et al., 2015) (Fig. 1B, C). The ensuing photocycle features a signaling state
122 characterized by a covalent thioadduct between the flavin chromophore and a conserved cysteine residue of
123 the receptor. The resultant flavin protonation is read out by a conserved glutamine and transduced in form
124 of hydrogen-bonding rearrangements. Intriguingly, neither the cysteine (Yee et al., 2015) nor the glutamine
125 (Dietler et al., 2022) are strictly required for signal transduction; their removal can modulate the absolute
126 light sensitivity and dark recovery of the receptor but generally impairs the fidelity of signaling. With certain
127 exceptions (Rivera-Cancel et al., 2014), bacterial LOV receptors are parallel homodimers that exhibit a range
128 of associated effector modules (Glantz et al., 2016). Other optogenetic tools used in bacteria are based on
129 BLUF photoreceptors (Gomelsky and Klug, 2002). These parallel homodimeric receptors also bind flavin-
130 nucleotide chromophores and thereby sense blue light but differ from LOV receptors in their photochemistry
131 and the structural signal output generated upon photon absorption.

132 BphPs and CBCRs are members of the phytochrome superfamily which covalently bind linear
133 tetrapyrrole (bilin) chromophores that undergo light-driven *Z/E* isomerization. These receptors are generally
134 photochromic with one light color driving the *Z*→*E* isomerization, and another light color promoting the *E*→*Z*
135 transition. The photosensory core modules (PCM) of BphPs comprise three concatenated domains, denoted
136 PAS, GAF, and PHY (Essen et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2008). A biliverdin (BV) chromophore nestles within the
137 GAF moiety and cycles between its *Z* and *E* isomers that absorb red (ca. 650-700 nm) and far-red light (ca.
138 700-750 nm), and that are hence referred to as the Pr and Pfr states (Fig. 1B, D) (Butler et al., 1959). The bilin
139 isomerization couples to a long protein loop, the so-called tongue, emanating from the PHY domain and
140 causes its refolding from a β hairpin in the *Z* isomer to an α helix in the *E* isomer (Anders et al., 2013; Takala
141 et al., 2014). BphPs commonly occur as homodimers, mostly in parallel orientation, and the light-dependent
142 tongue refolding prompts a pivot motion of the two monomeric units. Conventional BphPs assume the *Z*
143 isomer (Pr) as their dark-adapted state, rather than the *E* isomer (Pfr) in the so-called bathyphytochromes.
144 Cyanobacterial phytochromes, exemplified by Cph1 from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803, use the reduced bilin
145 phycocyanobilin (PCB) instead of BV, but resemble BphPs in other regards. Most CBCRs equally use PCB as
146 their light-sensitive pigment but offer compacter architecture in that their PCMs consist of sole GAF domains.
147 Often, CBCR modules are found within serially connected arrays of tandem CBCR and GAF domains (Rockwell
148 et al., 2013). Apart from their smaller footprint, CBCRs garner additional interest because of the diverse
149 photocycles and color sensitivity evidenced in different members of this photoreceptor family (Fushimi and
150 Narikawa, 2019). For instance, the CBCR histidine kinase CcaS from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803, which is
151 frequently used in bacterial optogenetics (Tabor et al., 2011), adopts the *Z*-configured Pg state in darkness
152 that can be converted by green light (ca. 500-600 nm) to the *E*-configured red-light-absorbing Pr state (ca.
153 600-700 nm) (Hirose et al., 2008) (Fig. 1B). Irrespective of the enormous color diversity across the CBCR clade,
154 the principal photochemical reaction triggered by light is the photoreversible *Z*↔*E* isomerization of the bilin
155 chromophore around its C15=C16 double bond (Fushimi and Narikawa, 2019). In nature, CBCR receptors
156 often function as sensor histidine kinases (SHK) but other effectors also occur (Blain-Hartung et al., 2018).
157 Although not yet harnessed for optogenetic actuation in bacteria, a subset of CBCRs incorporate BV rather
158 than PCB, thus resulting in a red-shift of the absorbance spectra in the *Z* and *E* states (Narikawa et al., 2015).

159 Only identified a decade ago (Ortiz-Guerrero et al., 2011), the CarH-type photoreceptors represent a
160 special case as they feature an irreversible photocycle revolving around 5'-desoxyadenosyl cobalamin
161 (vitamin B₁₂) chromophores. Green-light absorption (ca. 500-600 nm) ruptures the metalorganic bond
162 between cobalt and the adenosyl moiety and thereby prompts dissociation of the homotetrameric CarH into
163 monomers (Jost et al., 2015; Ortiz-Guerrero et al., 2011).

164 A necessary requirement for optogenetic regulation is the *in situ* assembly of the apo-photoreceptor
165 with its chromophore to form the functional holo-receptor. Chromophore uptake and, in case of BphPs and

166 CBCRs, its covalent attachment generally proceed autonomously and do not require additional factors. As
167 described above, LOV and BLUF receptors harbor flavin-nucleotide pigments which are universally present in
168 cells as redox-active cofactors. By contrast, other photoreceptor families rely on chromophores that are
169 specific to certain organisms and may not be present by default in many prokaryotes. The BV and PCB
170 chromophores of BphPs and CBCRs are routinely supplied via coexpression of enzymes that generate these
171 bilins from heme. Heme oxygenase (HO), most often HO1 from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 (Mukougawa et
172 al., 2006; Tabor et al., 2011), mediates the oxidative cleavage of heme to BV. In turn, BV can be reduced to
173 PCB, usually in a single step catalyzed by the ferredoxin-dependent oxidoreductase PcyA, also from *S. sp.* PCC
174 6803. Although certain microorganisms are capable of synthesizing cobalamin, many prokaryotes are not,
175 and the chromophore thus needs to be supplied exogenously for optogenetic applications of CarH and
176 related photoreceptors. By contrast, the heterologous *in situ* production of this chromophore via
177 coexpression of the biosynthetic machinery appears impractical, given that around 30 genes are involved
178 (Fang et al., 2018).

179 Light-dependent signal transduction

180 Before treating in detail the strategies for light-regulated bacterial expression realized to date, we briefly
181 consider general aspects and system characteristics that pertain to optogenetic applications (Ziegler and
182 Möglich, 2015). As introduced above, sensory photoreceptors are in photodynamic equilibrium between
183 their dark-adapted resting state and light-adapted signaling state. The response of a given optogenetic circuit
184 – i.e. in the present context, the expression output generated – will not only depend on the fractional
185 population of these two states but also on the specific activities associated with them (Fig. 2A). In case of
186 light-activated circuits, the signaling state has higher specific activity than the resting state, whereas for light-
187 repressed circuits, it is the opposite. Even if all photoreceptors dwell in their low-activity state, optogenetic
188 circuits will generally produce a basal output, also referred to as leakiness. Once all photoreceptors are
189 shifted to their high-activity state, maximal gene-expression output of the circuit will be obtained. The ratio
190 of maximal over basal activity is usually denoted as the dynamic range (or, regulatory efficiency/factor) (Fig.
191 2A), and optogenetic strategies commonly strive to optimize this parameter. The dynamic range is generally
192 improved more effectively by reducing the basal activity rather than by increasing the maximal activity
193 (Ziegler and Möglich, 2015). Another important consideration is how the interconversion between resting
194 and signaling states varies with applied light dose. To the extent it has been studied, many photoreceptors
195 employed for regulating bacterial gene expression follow simple dose-saturation relationships, i.e. the
196 degree of receptor activation increases hyperbolically with light dose. The dose at which half-maximal
197 activation occurs determines the light sensitivity of a given system (Fig. 2A). Several factors can give rise to
198 cooperativity and thereby cause deviations from the hyperbolic relationship, often incurring sigmoidal or Hill-
199 type relationships. For instance, many, if not most, photoreceptors used in bacterial optogenetics act as

200 homodimers and therefore harbor two light-responsive monomers (Fig. 2B). Light-induced conversion of but
201 one of these monomers to the signaling state may impact differently on receptor activity, ranging from no
202 measurable change in output to full effect. As a case in point, the engineered SHK YF1 comprises two LOV
203 entities that can absorb light independently of each other (Möglich et al., 2009). Conversion of just one LOV
204 unit to the signaling state alters receptor activity to the same extent as if both LOV units were converted.
205 Moreover, cellular circuitry that translates photoreceptor activation into gene-expression output may also
206 yield cooperativity (Ziegler and Möglich, 2015). In a similar manner, such circuits could also experience
207 thresholding effects and hence deviate from simple dose-saturation relationships.

208 The light sensitivity of optogenetic circuits (Fig. 2A) is fundamentally linked to how efficiently the
209 underlying sensory photoreceptors absorb light and then undergo productive photochemistry that
210 culminates in population of the signaling state (see Fig. 1C, D). Put simply, what are the extinction coefficients
211 and quantum yields for productive photochemistry in different photoreceptors? Although not all relevant
212 photoreceptors have been characterized in this regard, general information for individual photoreceptor
213 classes exists. By virtue of their flavin-nucleotide chromophores, LOV receptors absorb blue light with a
214 maximum around 450 nm where the molar extinction coefficient is around 10,000 to 15,000 $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ (Fig.
215 1B). The overall quantum yield for formation of the thioadduct signaling state via an intermediate triplet
216 state amounts to around 0.3 – 0.4 for the widely used *Avena sativa* phototropin 1 LOV2 (AsLOV2) module
217 and to around 0.5 for *Bacillus subtilis* YtvA (Kennis et al., 2003; Losi et al., 2002) (Fig. 1C). Bacterial
218 phytochromes absorb light in their Pr and Pfr states with maxima at around 700 nm and 750 nm, respectively,
219 and with molar extinction coefficients between $\sim 70,000 - 90,000 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ (Fig. 1B). Not least because the
220 absorption within this spectral band (the so-called Q band) strongly depends on protonation of the bilin
221 chromophore, the molar extinction coefficient at the absorbance maximum varies considerably across
222 individual BphPs. Cyanobacterial phytochromes absorb at shorter wavelength owing to the less extended
223 conjugated π electron system in PCB compared to BV. For both BphPs and Cph1, the quantum yields for
224 productive Pr \leftrightarrow Pfr photoconversion are relatively low, on the order of 0.15 – 0.2 (Dasgupta et al., 2009; Toh
225 et al., 2010) (Fig. 1D). CcaS, as the CBCR representative most relevant for bacterial optogenetics, maximally
226 absorbs at 535 nm in its dark-adapted Pg state with a molar extinction coefficient of 27,000 $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ (Hirose
227 et al., 2010). Once converted to the Pr state, the absorbance maximum shifts to 670 nm, and the extinction
228 coefficient amounts to 30,000 $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$. The quantum yields for driving the Z/E isomerization and conversion
229 between the two states of CBCRs are about 0.3 – 0.4 (Slavov et al., 2015), i.e. significantly higher than for
230 BphPs.

231 Intricately connected to the absorption and photoconversion properties is light delivery *in situ*. The
232 requirements and boundary conditions for light delivery are determined by the given optogenetic
233 application. As detailed below, light-regulated gene expression has been applied to bacteria in diverse

234 contexts, including in dense liquid culture and inside animal hosts. Irrespective of the exact application
235 scenario, light scattering generally scales with the inverse fourth power of wavelength, thus causing shorter
236 wavelengths to be scattered more strongly than long ones. This phenomenon accounts in part for the better
237 tissue penetration of longer wavelengths within the near-UV to NIR region of the electromagnetic spectrum
238 (Weissleder, 2001). Light penetration through biological tissue is additionally limited because of absorption
239 by hemoglobin and other biomolecules. Depending on wavelength, the amount of light that may be delivered
240 per unit time can be narrowly restricted before phototoxicity sets in which may harm living cells and may
241 obscure light-dependent signaling responses. As one workaround, upconverting nanoparticles (UNP) have
242 been used to toggle blue-light-sensitive optogenetic circuits inside the digestive tract of animals (Cui et al.,
243 2021; Pan et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2020). These nanoparticles are activated by NIR light (e.g., 980 nm) which
244 penetrates biological tissue more readily and is less phototoxic than blue light. Multiple absorption events
245 generate a metastable state in the UNPs, out of which a photon of shorter wavelength, e.g., of blue color, is
246 emitted that in turn can trigger the optogenetic system. As delivery to the target site *in situ* is required,
247 pertinent approaches are no longer entirely genetically encoded which can be a limitation, depending on use
248 case. A potential remedy are optogenetic circuits that can be triggered by red light such as the Cph8:OmpR
249 setup (Levskaia et al., 2005) or the recently developed pREDusk/pREDawn systems (Multamäki et al., 2022).
250 As a case in point, pREDawn was activated by red light at therapeutically safe intensities through materials
251 with the optical properties of mouse tissue. To potentially enhance sensitivity of a given optogenetic circuit,
252 one might consider modulation of the absolute light sensitivity which is principally governed by the molar
253 extinction coefficient (see Fig. 1B) and quantum yield for productive photochemistry. However, modifications
254 to the photoreceptor that would alter this quantum yield are relatively little explored. Moreover, at least for
255 certain photoreceptor classes the experimentally observed photoconversion efficiencies may already
256 approach the physically possible limit, arguably obtained upon ample optimization during evolution.
257 (Evidently, the quantum yield can only be unity or less.) A different and more accessible route towards
258 varying the effective light sensitivity is provided by modulation of the dark-recovery kinetics that determine
259 how fast a photoreceptor thermally reverts from its signaling state to the resting state. In particular for LOV
260 receptors (Christie et al., 2007; Kawano et al., 2013; Pudasaini et al., 2015), but also for BphPs (Yang et al.,
261 2007, 2009), residue exchanges nearby the chromophore are known to decelerate or accelerate the dark
262 recovery. Optogenetic applications, especially those involving light-regulated gene expression, are frequently
263 performed under photostationary conditions, and the underlying photoreceptors may undergo repeated
264 cycles of photoactivation and subsequent recovery. The fraction of the receptor in its signaling state is hence
265 governed by the effective light sensitivity, i.e. the balance between the velocities of the light-driven activation
266 and the passive recovery (Ziegler and Möglich, 2015). The targeted variation of recovery kinetics thus
267 provides a handle to substantially modulate the sensitivity of optogenetic circuits at photostationary state
268 (Hennemann et al., 2018; Ziegler and Möglich, 2015). However, caution must be exerted, as certain residue

269 exchanges were found to not only modulate the recovery kinetics but to also negatively affect signal
270 transduction, e.g., (Diensthuber et al., 2014; Dietler et al., 2022).

271 The reactions leading to population and depletion, respectively, of the signaling state also contribute
272 to the temporal resolution that can be achieved for a specific optogenetic application. Since the
273 photochemical reactions playing out in photoreceptors after light absorption are fast compared to
274 downstream responses, they are generally not limiting for the turn-on kinetics with which an optogenetic
275 circuit can be triggered. Rather, these kinetics are more often limited by light delivery *in situ*, see above, and
276 slower subsequent reaction steps. The latter consideration certainly holds true for light-regulated gene-
277 expression systems which in most cases realize regulation at the transcriptional level, see control points for
278 optogenetic regulation below. Although the experimental data on this aspect are sparse, several optogenetic
279 setups for light-regulated expression in bacteria exhibited significant changes in expression levels within
280 around half an hour after light exposure, with the response taking several hours to manifest to full degree
281 (Multamäki et al., 2022; Ohlendorf et al., 2012; Ong and Tabor, 2018; Ranzani et al., 2022). The dark-recovery
282 kinetics greatly differ across photoreceptor families and their individual members. For example, plant
283 phototropin LOV domains, exemplified by the widely deployed AsLOV2, recover to the resting state with time
284 constants around 100 s or less (Kottke et al., 2003) which contrasts with the much slower kinetics on the
285 order of thousands of seconds evidenced in bacterial and fungal LOV domains (Conrad et al., 2013; Losi et
286 al., 2002; Möglich et al., 2009; Weber et al., 2019; Zoltowski et al., 2007). The dark recovery in BphPs is
287 commonly multiphasic and progresses over several thousands of seconds (Multamäki et al., 2021). Within
288 the CBCR family, the dark-reversion kinetics greatly vary and can take between seconds and several hours to
289 complete (Chen et al., 2012; Fushimi et al., 2017). As discussed above, at least for certain photoreceptor
290 families, residue exchanges near the chromophore have been identified which greatly change the recovery
291 kinetics (Fig. 2C). Moreover, the dark recovery is often associated with sizeable activation energies which
292 renders its kinetics strongly dependent on temperature. Whereas the dark recovery usually follows single- or
293 multiexponential courses, the reversion of the biological output upon withdrawal of light need not
294 necessarily track this time course. As experimentally shown and discussed in Fig. 2D, oligomeric
295 photoreceptors may react to light cooperatively. For instance, blue light converts the homodimeric YF1
296 receptor from kinase to phosphatase activity (Möglich et al., 2009). Returned to darkness, the original kinase
297 activity recovers in sigmoidal manner as it requires the reversion of both its LOV monomers to their resting
298 states. Photochromic receptors, such as the particularly widely used SHKs CcaS (Hirose et al., 2008) and Cph8
299 (Levskaya et al., 2005), enable the active off-switching by absorption of a second photon of different color
300 (Fig. 1A, 2E). Thereby, reversion to the resting state can be much accelerated to the extent that it is only
301 limited by light delivery, as discussed above for the forward reaction. The ability to fast and photoreversibly
302 toggle between two activity states provides a decisive advantage for many use cases, not least for the all-
303 optical feedback control of bioproduction processes (Davidson et al., 2013; Kumar and Khammash, 2022;

304 Miliás-Argeitis et al., 2016; Steel et al., 2020). Pertinent applications have been realized for the green-/red-
305 light-responsive CcaRS two-component system. By continuously monitoring the output of the optogenetic
306 system, e.g., cell density or reporter fluorescence, the CcaS receptor can be clamped at desired ratios of its
307 P_g and P_r states, and the system output can thereby be controlled with precision in time exceeding that for
308 non-photochromic receptors. Although not studied in detail, sensory photoreceptors exhibit low
309 photofatigue and can be excited multiple times with little, if any, loss of responsiveness (Fig. 2F). Principally,
310 at some point photodamage will accumulate, but for current applications to optogenetically control bacterial
311 expression, there is little indication that photofatigue could be limiting.

312 Taken together, the different photoreceptor families each offer traits that can be advantageous or
313 limiting, depending on the application scenario. The photochromic, bidirectional toggling of optogenetic
314 circuits is clearly beneficial for many situations. Moreover, the systems based on CBCRs and BphPs generally
315 absorb at longer wavelengths than the widespread blue-light-sensitive LOV receptors, which may prove
316 advantageous when light delivery is limiting. At the same time, CBCRs and especially BphPs absorb across
317 substantial portions of the near-UV to NIR spectrum which may complicate multiplexed applications with
318 other photoreceptors and fluorescent reporters. For instance, the PCM of the *Deinococcus radiodurans* BphP
319 (*DrPCM*) can not only be activated by red light but also by blue light, owing to its absorption in the Soret band
320 around 400 nm (see Fig. 1A) (Gasser et al., 2014). It may furthermore be challenging to fully interconvert
321 between the two spectral states because the absorbance spectra of the two metastable states in
322 photochromic receptors generally overlap (see Fig. 1A). Moreover, the quantum yields for the light-driven,
323 forward and reverse reactions may substantially differ. As a case in point, the *DrPCM*, often used in
324 optogenetics (Lehtinen et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2021), exhibited sluggish P_r→P_g reversion when illuminated
325 with NIR light (Etzl et al., 2018; Gasser et al., 2014; Stabel et al., 2019). The *in situ* supply of the chromophores
326 for CBCRs and BphPs is usually not limiting as bilin synthesis can readily be achieved via coexpression of HO
327 (and PcyA) and is therefore not restricting most bacterial applications. In summary, there is no clear-cut case
328 for generally preferring one photoreceptor class over another. Rather, the availability of several classes with
329 different light sensitivity can be considered an advantage as it enables multiplexed applications of light-
330 regulated bacterial expression, see below (Fernandez-Rodriguez et al., 2017; Multamäki et al., 2022; Tabor
331 et al., 2011). Lastly, several strategies that proved successful for the design of optogenetic circuits can be
332 often extended to other photoreceptor classes. This is particularly true for circuits that rely on light-
333 controlled oligomerization reactions and, to lesser extent, two-component systems, both of which we discuss
334 in the next section.

335 Allosteric mechanisms in light-dependent signal transduction

336 Recent years have witnessed the advent of various setups for the light-dependent control of bacterial gene
337 expression (Table 1, Fig. 3). Despite this welcome diversity, the vast majority of approaches employ one of
338 merely three principal mechanisms to achieve light sensitivity: i. two-component systems; ii. oligomerization;
339 iii. second messengers.

340 Light-responsive two-component systems

341 In their canonical form (Buschiazzo and Trajtenberg, 2019; Lazar and Tabor, 2021; Möglich, 2019), two-
342 component systems (TCS) comprise a sensor histidine kinase (SHK) and a response regulator (RR) (Fig. 4C).
343 While SHKs often span the plasma membrane, light-sensitive SHKs, based on LOV, CBCR, or BphP sensor
344 modules, are soluble proteins. To date, the three most widely used light-responsive TCSs are based on the
345 CcaS CBCR (Ong and Tabor, 2018; Tabor et al., 2011), the cyanobacterial Cph8 (Levskaya et al., 2005; Schmidl
346 et al., 2014), and the LOV receptor YF1 (Möglich et al., 2009; Ohlendorf et al., 2012). SHKs adopt two principal
347 functional states that exert kinase and phosphatase activities, respectively, towards their cognate RRs
348 (Möglich, 2019; Möglich et al., 2009; Russo and Silhavy, 1993). In their kinase-active state, SHKs
349 autophosphorylate at a conserved histidine residue and transfer phosphate groups to a conserved aspartate
350 within the RR. When active as a phosphatase, the SHK mediates the hydrolysis of the phosphate anhydride
351 in the phosphorylated RR. The biological output, most often DNA binding and transcriptional activation, is
352 primarily determined by the degree of RR phosphorylation and hence by the net balance between the
353 elementary kinase and phosphatase activities. Although the tug of war between the opposing kinase and
354 phosphatase reactions can incur futile ATP hydrolysis, it also provides the basis for highly stringent and steep
355 signaling responses. The recognition between SHK and RR is highly specific, and multiple coexisting TCS inside
356 the bacterial cell are well insulated from each other to prevent undesired crosstalk (Skerker et al., 2008).
357 However, heterologous applications of TCSs, e.g., for light-regulated gene expression, may potentially suffer
358 from inadvertent crosstalk with endogenous SHKs and RRs, although these aspects are rarely investigated in
359 detail. Similarly, the SHK and its cognate RR may also be subject to non-enzymatic phosphorylation by
360 reactive phosphate species, such as acetyl phosphate. Not least because of these considerations it becomes
361 clear that usually both the kinase and phosphatase modes are important for (heterologous) applications of
362 TCSs. At the molecular level, the transition between kinase and phosphatase modes is mediated by structural
363 rearrangements within the histidine-kinase effector module (Möglich, 2019; Trajtenberg et al., 2016). Signals
364 emanating from the (light-sensitive) SHK sensor module travel to the effector through α -helical coiled coils
365 which exhibit a seven-residue, i.e. heptad, periodicity in their structure. Targeted length modification of the
366 coiled-coil linker thus provides a handle for reprogramming the signal response of SHKs (Möglich et al., 2009;
367 Nakajima et al., 2016b; Ohlendorf et al., 2016). For instance, elongation of said linker converted YF1 from a
368 blue-light-repressed net histidine kinase to a light-activated one (Ohlendorf et al., 2016). Alternatively,

369 certain point mutations in the LOV photosensor sufficed to invert the response of YF1 to light (Diensthuber
370 et al., 2014; Gleichmann et al., 2013).

371 Light-dependent oligomerization reactions

372 Many processes in biology rely on protein oligomerization and therefore lend themselves to optogenetic
373 regulation via light-dependent association and dissociation reactions. This notion is duly reflected in the
374 manifold setups for light-regulated bacterial gene expression that harness photoreceptor pairs which
375 associate or dissociate under light, e.g., (Chen et al., 2016; Dietler et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020; Romano et al.,
376 2021). These approaches have in common that the intrinsic oligomeric state, in most cases dimeric, of a
377 target effector, e.g., a transcriptional activator, is disrupted, usually by protein truncation (Fig. 4A, B). The
378 truncated protein ideally has little remaining dimerization capability, and its biological activity is thus turned
379 off. Ligation to photoassociating or photodissociating photoreceptor pairs can restore the dimeric state in
380 dependence of light and thus regain biological activity. The application scope of light-dependent association
381 reactions extends to split proteins which are severed into two parts with low mutual affinity (Baumschlager
382 et al., 2017; Sheets et al., 2020) (Fig. 4A). Again, light-dependent heterodimerization of the split fragments
383 restores biological activity. A number of protein modules, mostly from the LOV receptor family, serve as light-
384 activated dimerization modules for the optogenetic control of prokaryotic expression. As the most
385 extensively used module, the short-LOV protein Vivid from *Neurospora crassa* (*NcVVD*) associates under blue
386 light into a homodimer (Vaidya et al., 2011; Zoltowski and Crane, 2008). By modifying residues at the dimer
387 interface, the so-called Magnet pairs were devised which assemble into a heterodimer under blue light while
388 the homodimer affinity of each Magnet component alone is low (Kawano et al., 2015). Similar to *NcVVD*, the
389 LOV domains *VfLOV* and *PtLOV* from aureochromes of stramenopile algae (e.g., *Vaucheria frigida*) and
390 diatoms (e.g., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*) associate into homodimers upon blue-light absorption (Pfeifer et
391 al., 2010; Takahashi et al., 2007). The short-LOV receptor from *Rhodobacter sphaeroides* (*RsLOV*) exhibits the
392 opposite response to photon absorption and adopts homodimeric and monomeric states in darkness and
393 under blue light, respectively (Conrad et al., 2013). The optogenetic output generated by systems employing
394 light-regulated association is fundamentally determined by the law of mass action for the oligomerization
395 equilibria in darkness and under light (Fig. 2B). As illustrated for a homodimeric photoreceptor, the dimeric
396 fraction of the receptor most strongly varies with illumination at a concentration between the dissociation
397 constants for the dark- and light-adapted states. By contrast, the ratio of the dimeric fractions under light
398 and in darkness monotonically decreases with the receptor concentration. Depending on the value of the
399 dissociation constants, only certain concentration windows may support robust light-induced signaling
400 responses (Fig. 2B). Precise data on the light-dependent dissociation constants of photoreceptors are
401 lamentably sparse but values around 10 μM and 0.5 μM were reported for the light-adapted states of *NcVVD*
402 and *VfLOV*, respectively (Nakatani and Hisatomi, 2015; Zoltowski and Crane, 2008), with the affinity in the

403 dark-adapted state too weak to be reliably determined. The dissociation constant for the dark-adapted *RsLOV*
404 homodimer amounted to 40 μM (Dietler et al., 2021), whereas the interaction in the light-adapted state was
405 too weak to be measured. Certain LOV receptors, including *RsLOV*, are intrinsically temperature-sensitive
406 and may exhibit reduced light responsiveness at elevated temperatures (Benman et al., 2022; Dietler et al.,
407 2021). Numerous optogenetic applications in mammalian cells employ plant cryptochrome 2 (Bugaj et al.,
408 2013; Kennedy et al., 2010), the iLID system (Guntas et al., 2015), the UV-responsive UVR8 (Chen et al., 2013),
409 or plant phytochromes (Golonka et al., 2019; Levskaya et al., 2009) to effect light-dependent oligomerization
410 reactions. To date, these and yet other dimerization systems (Klewer and Wu, 2019) have not seen much use
411 in prokaryotes, likely due to the availability of the above LOV-based, well-performing systems and, at least in
412 certain cases, challenges in the heterologous expression of plant photoreceptors.

413 Light-controlled second-messenger signaling

414 A third group of approaches for light-regulated gene expression in bacteria harness the production of second
415 messengers which, among other responses, can activate transcription (Fig. 4D). The two most prominent
416 types within this group are based on either 3',5'-cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) or 3',5'-cyclic
417 diguanylate (c-di-GMP). Several photo-activated adenylyl cyclases (PAC), which catalyze cAMP production
418 upon light stimulation, were identified in nature or constructed by protein engineering. The most widely used
419 PAC is the one from *Beggiatoa* sp. (Ryu et al., 2010; Stierl et al., 2011) that encompasses a BLUF photosensor
420 and upregulates cAMP synthesis under blue light by several hundred-fold. Other PACs bear BphP and CBCR
421 photosensor modules, thereby unlocking longer wavelengths for the optogenetic regulation of cAMP
422 metabolism, but generally suffer from comparatively low dynamic ranges (Blain-Hartung et al., 2018; Ettl et
423 al., 2018; Fushimi et al., 2017; Ryu and Gomelsky, 2014; Stüven et al., 2019). By contrast, c-di-GMP cyclases
424 linked to BphP PCMs can exhibit exquisite dynamic ranges for regulation by red light (Gourinchas et al., 2019;
425 Ryu and Gomelsky, 2014). Signal transduction in these homodimeric photoactivated cAMP and c-di-GMP
426 cyclases employs light-dependent rearrangements within a helical bundle or coiled coil connecting the
427 photosensor and effector moieties (Gourinchas et al., 2017). The light-modulated levels of the cyclic
428 nucleotides are linked to gene expression via transcription factors that are sensitive to these second
429 messengers, see control points for optogenetic regulation below.

430 Comparison of allosteric strategies

431 Light-sensitive TCSs currently dominate the optogenetic control of bacterial expression. This predominance
432 may in part reflect the comparatively early availability of the YF1 and CcaS SHKs which afforded stringent
433 light responses (Möglich et al., 2009; Ohlendorf et al., 2012; Tabor et al., 2011). As another potential reason,
434 TCSs can mediate particularly stringent and pronounced signal responses, owing to the dual kinase and
435 phosphatase activities of their SHKs, see above (Möglich, 2019; Russo and Silhavy, 1993). This inherent

436 property of most SHKs almost certainly accounts for the predominance of TCSs in bacterial signal
437 transduction and may also explain their success in bacterial optogenetics. As implied by their name, TCSs
438 require at least two polypeptide components, namely the SHK and the RR, plus potentially additional
439 accessory components, e.g., for chromophore production. This contrasts with systems based on light-
440 dependent homodimerization which experience increased use and are mostly realized as single components
441 (Chen et al., 2016; Dietler et al., 2021; Motta-Mena et al., 2014; Romano et al., 2021). The simpler
442 architecture of these setups appears immediately attractive, not least because it entails a smaller genetic
443 footprint, i.e. the total size of the gene(s) encoding the optogenetic circuit. However, it is unclear to what
444 extent the simpler buildup plays out in practice and grants relevant benefits for current optogenetic
445 applications in bacteria. One might implicitly assume that single-component systems provide more stringent
446 and robust light responses, but this sentiment is not supported by the available data. In fact, thresholding
447 and saturation effects aside (see above), the response of any circuit that banks on oligomerization, be it light-
448 responsive or not, must evidently scale with protein concentration (Fig. 2B). Variations in protein
449 concentration could for instance arise from expression differences between cells, even within a monoclonal
450 population (Ziegler and Möglich, 2015). As far as it has been studied, this principal aspect is borne out by
451 experiment (Romano et al., 2021). Although the performance of TCSs will also depend on the amounts of the
452 SHK and RR components (Schmidl et al., 2014), it is potentially less affected by concentration variation, given
453 that both the elementary kinase and phosphatase reactions depend on the SHK and RR concentrations in the
454 same order. Moreover, the binding mode of the RR to the SHK is strikingly similar in the kinase and
455 phosphatase states (Möglich, 2019; Trajtenberg et al., 2016). In line with this observation, the affinity of the
456 *D. radiodurans* BphP (*DrBphP*) for its RR is little affected by illumination with red and far-red light (Multamäki
457 et al., 2021).

458 Control points for optogenetic regulation of bacterial expression

459 After covering fundamentals of optogenetics in bacteria, we now turn to concrete strategies which subjected
460 bacterial gene expression to light control. As stipulated by the central dogma of molecular biology (Crick,
461 1958), the genetic information laid down in the DNA is transcribed into RNA before being translated into
462 protein. Optogenetics can principally exert control at different stages of this event chain, as borne out by
463 diverse strategies realized to date for light-regulated expression in *Escherichia coli* and other bacteria (Table
464 1). Although the most important and most frequently controlled step is transcription initiation, other stages
465 were also controlled optogenetically (Fig. 3). When applying optogenetics to the control of bacterial gene
466 expression, a key consideration is how efficient the regulation by light will eventually be. Put another way,
467 what is the dynamic range for regulation by light in the diverse optogenetic strategies at hand (Fig. 2A)?
468 Although this question is phrased easily, it is very challenging to answer conclusively. The original reports on
469 the development of the respective optogenetic tools commonly assessed the dynamic range of regulation

470 using reporter genes, in most cases fluorescent proteins, but also β -galactosidase (LacZ). However, the
471 individual studies greatly differ in terms of reporter identity, experimental conditions, data evaluation, and
472 background correction, all of which impact on the attainable regulatory efficiency. Even though a systematic
473 side-by-side comparison between different optogenetic strategies for the control of bacterial gene
474 expression seems principally desirable, no unbiased analyses have yet been undertaken to this effect. Such
475 endeavors would in any case be fraught with substantial challenges, not least that the experimental setting
476 selected for comparison may inadvertently favor one or another of the strategies. Against this backdrop, in
477 the following we refrain from a quantitative comparison of the various optogenetic systems and refer to the
478 dynamic ranges of light regulation provided in the original reports or, where applicable, their later
479 improvements (see Table 1). When appraising the regulatory efficiency for a given setup, one should also
480 consider at which stage of the gene expression process the setup acts. By and large, the response to signal,
481 light or otherwise, is often more pronounced in circuits that operate at the transcriptional level compared
482 to, for instance, the translational level. Beyond dynamic range and basal activity, other aspects are also
483 important for practical application, e.g., sensitivity, light color, phototoxicity, cytotoxicity, and response
484 kinetics, as outlined above. Potential crosstalk with the endogenous bacterial signaling circuits is relevant as
485 well but rarely probed in detail; hence, little concrete data are available on that score. Given that certain
486 optogenetic tools are based on common *E. coli* transcription factors (Chen et al., 2016; Levskaya et al., 2005;
487 Romano et al., 2021), interference with the intrinsic signaling pathways and inadvertent activation of
488 endogenous genes may arise (Stringer et al., 2014; Wade et al., 2005). Although multiple two-component
489 systems are usually well insulated from another (Skerker et al., 2008), interactions with endogenous cellular
490 constituents cannot be ruled out *a priori* for these setups either.

491 Optogenetic control upstream of transcription

492 Several strategies for the optogenetic regulation of bacterial expression act upstream of transcription
493 initiation and control by light the availability of the DNA template to be transcribed (mechanism ① in Fig. 3)
494 or the activity of the RNA polymerase (mechanism ②). Although light-regulated versions of the site-specific
495 recombinase Cre were established in mammalian cells early on (Kawano et al., 2016; Kennedy et al., 2010;
496 Meador et al., 2019; Morikawa et al., 2020; Taslimi et al., 2016), a corresponding system for bacteria arrived
497 only more recently (Sheets et al., 2020). In all cases, the Cre recombinase is split into N- and C-terminal halves
498 that by themselves have little mutual affinity and accordingly low catalytic activity. Via conjugation to
499 photoreceptor pairs that associate under light, the fragments can be assembled, and recombinase action is
500 restored. Whereas several photoactivable Cre recombinases for eukaryotic use rely on plant Cry2 and its
501 interacting CIB protein (Kennedy et al., 2010), the prokaryotic setup harnesses the light-induced dimerization
502 of NcVVD or its Magnets derivatives (Sheets et al., 2020). The light-dependent activity of this system, called
503 OptoCreVvd, was assessed with a reporter cassette comprising a transcriptional terminator flanked by *loxP*

504 sites and followed by a gene encoding a red-fluorescent protein. Cre action promoted removal of the
505 terminator sequence and hence led to an upregulation of reporter fluorescence by around 12-fold under blue
506 light compared to darkness. Interestingly, the dynamic range of light regulation was higher when using the
507 homodimerizing *NcVVD* module rather than the heterodimerizing Magnets. Owing to the modularity of the
508 setup, the design principle readily extended to the Flp recombinase which operates at the target FRT sites
509 that are orthogonal to *loxP*. It is worth noting, that although light-induced reconstitution of the split
510 recombinase fragments is fully reversible, the resultant recombination events are essentially irreversible
511 under the chosen experimental conditions, which contrasts with essentially all other control points for the
512 optogenetic regulation of bacterial expression. Depending on the application scenario, the effective
513 irreversibility of the light-induced response can be advantageous. At the same time, irreversible systems
514 generally mandate minimal basal (dark) activity, lest activation occurs prematurely. Even if low, basal activity
515 might lead to gradual triggering of the optogenetic circuit to extents that will vary with the time that circuit
516 is present in the bacteria.

517 Optogenetic control of bacterial expression was also accomplished at the level of RNA polymerase
518 activity (mechanism ② in Fig. 3) by two groups concurrently (Baumschlager et al., 2017; Han et al., 2017)
519 (Fig. 4A). In both approaches, the activity of the viral T7 RNA polymerase (T7RNAP) was subjected to light
520 control by fragmentation into two segments and linkage to the photoassociating Magnets or *NcVVD*. Doing
521 so allowed the upregulation of target-gene expression under blue light by up to several hundred-fold
522 (Baumschlager et al., 2017), depending on the split site within the T7RNAP. Intriguingly, gene expression
523 could also be upregulated by light to substantial degree if only one of the two T7RNAP fragments was ligated
524 with either *NcVVD* or one of the two Magnets (Han et al., 2017). Similarly, light-induced upregulation of gene
525 expression resulted when said Magnet component was inserted into the T7RNAP between its N- and C-
526 terminal halves. While maintaining stringent light responses, this design is realized as a single polypeptide
527 component which should render its performance less dependent on its overall cellular concentration, see
528 above. Taken together, the findings indicate that the *NcVVD* LOV module and the derivative Magnets are
529 capable of mediating different allosteric responses beyond mere dimerization. A later study also harnessed
530 split T7RNAP to optogenetically regulate the expression of genes underlying lycopene biosynthesis in *E. coli*
531 (Raghavan et al., 2020). In marked contrast to the earlier studies, T7RNAP was activated by red-light-induced
532 intein splicing, akin to a previous implementation in yeast (Tyszkiewicz and Muir, 2008). To render protein
533 splicing dependent on red light, a bipartite split intein was linked to the PCM of *A. thaliana* PhyB and its
534 phytochrome-interacting factor (PIF) 3, respectively (Raghavan et al., 2020). Red light thus promoted
535 assembly of the two split-intein components and allowed protein splicing to ensue. Using this strategy,
536 unmodified and hence fully active T7RNAP could be obtained upon light-induced intein processing. Light-
537 induced activation in this manner is largely irreversible, excepting eventual T7RNAP turnover. Upon T7RNAP
538 activation under red light, the lycopene production rose 5-fold. Beyond that, a key advance of the study is

539 the functional expression of a plant phytochrome and its interacting factor in *E. coli*. Not only will this
540 development pave the way towards further applications in bacteria, but also it stands to benefit the
541 mechanistic study and possible modification of the PhyB:PIF interaction.

542 T7RNAP is an attractive target for optogenetic intervention as it recognizes promoters that are
543 orthogonal to those served by the endogenous RNA polymerase (RNAP). By contrast, it is much more
544 challenging to optogenetically control the bacterial RNAP to thus enable the light-dependent expression of a
545 single or a few genes only. Although not realized to date, one principal avenue towards optogenetically
546 regulating the bacterial RNAP could be the construction of light-regulated orthogonal sigma factors that
547 recognize promoters not used by the endogenous sigma factors.

548 Optogenetic control of transcription

549 The vast majority of approaches for the optogenetic control of bacterial expression act at the level of
550 transcription initiation (mechanisms ③ and ④ in Fig. 3). Before treating them in detail, it is worth
551 recapitulating basic aspects of the underlying processes (Müller-Hill, 1996). Transcription is initiated by
552 promoter binding of the σ factor in complex with the RNAP, which in turn consists of two α and the β , β' , and
553 ω subunits. Bacterial promoters are recognized by specific sequence motifs upstream of the first transcribed
554 nucleotide, which is designated as the +1 position. Under normal conditions, the σ^{70} factor mediates the
555 transcription of most genes in *E. coli* and other bacteria. The σ^{70} factor binds and thereby recognizes two
556 conserved motifs centered around the -10 and -35 positions, with the former also known as the Pribnow box.
557 Other σ factors differ in the sequence and precise location of their cognate operator motifs, thus enabling
558 them to serve distinct sets of promoters. Once assembled at its promoter, the RNAP first dwells in its
559 initiation mode and mediates repeated abortive transcription events. Only upon transitioning to its
560 elongation mode, the RNAP clears the promoter and polymerizes mRNA in highly processive manner. The
561 inherent strength of a given σ^{70} -dependent promoter is largely governed by the sequences of the -10 and -
562 35 boxes, with transcription usually the higher the closer these sequences are to the consensus motifs.
563 However, even weak promoters commonly exhibit basal, if low, transcription levels in the absence of other
564 factors (see Fig. 2A). Transcription factors act by binding to specific operator sites near or within the
565 promoters and thereby facilitate or hinder transcription initiation and elongation (Fig. 3, 4B). Transcriptional
566 activators often assemble on DNA stretches upstream of the -35 box and aid recruitment of the RNAP via
567 productive interactions with the C-terminal domains (CTD) of the polymerase α subunits. Prominent
568 examples include the catabolite activator protein (Müller-Hill, 1996), also referred to as the catabolite
569 repressor protein, and the L-arabinose-inducible AraC (Stringer et al., 2014). By contrast, bacterial repressors
570 operate by interfering with binding of the σ factor and the RNAP, or with RNAP translocation and its
571 processive mRNA synthesis. Compared to activators, repressors therefore exhibit more diverse locations of
572 their operator sites, which are most frequently situated within or downstream of the promoter region. As a

573 case in point, the well-known LacI repressor controls transcription of the *lac* operon via two operator sites
574 upstream and downstream of the promoter in addition to the dominant operator site that interleaves with
575 the promoter (Müller-Hill, 1996). Taken together, the effect of transcription factors on bacterial transcription
576 is to some extent governed by where in relation to the transcription start site they bind. By the same token,
577 transcriptional activators can be leveraged as repressors by judiciously moving their operator sites, as for
578 instance shown for EL222 (Ding et al., 2020; Jayaraman et al., 2016) and CcaR (Ariyanti et al., 2021).

579 Two-component systems

580 As noted above, two-component systems are currently most widely used for the optogenetic regulation of
581 bacterial expression (Fig. 4C). Phosphorylation by the light-sensitive SHK generally activates the RR protein,
582 frequently prompting its dimerization, and enables its binding to target operator sites. These sites are
583 commonly located upstream of the -35 box and therefore allow productive interactions between the RR and
584 the α -CTD of the RNAP. The first light-sensitive TCS suitable for optogenetics in bacteria was devised on the
585 basis of the cyanobacterial Cph1 (Levskaya et al., 2005). Similar to pioneering work on light-inert, chimeric
586 SHKs (Utsumi et al., 1989), the Cph1 PCM was covalently coupled to the effector unit of the *E. coli* EnvZ SHK
587 which is engaged in osmosensing. In concert with the cognate RR OmpR, the resultant chimeric SHK Cph8
588 drove expression of a LacZ reporter in darkness, with an around 10-fold lower output under red light. As a
589 cyanobacterial phytochrome, Cph8 required the provision of the PCB chromophore to elicit light responses,
590 either via exogenous addition or via coexpression of the *ho* and *pcyA* genes (Tabor et al., 2011). By optimizing
591 the Cph8, HO, and PcyA expression levels and the target promoter sequence, the dynamic range of the
592 Cph8:OmpR TCS was later improved to around 70-fold (Schmidl et al., 2014). The introduction of an inverter-
593 gene cassette, based on the λ phage cI repressor and its target pR promoter (Elowitz and Leibler, 2000),
594 reprogrammed the light response, resulting in higher expression under red light than in darkness (Tabor et
595 al., 2011).

596 Next, the recombination of the LOV photosensor module of *B. subtilis* YtvA and the effector module of
597 *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* FixL yielded the widely used, blue-light-responsive SHK YF1 (Möglich et al., 2009).
598 In darkness, YF1 readily phosphorylates its cognate RR FixJ, also from *B. japonicum*, but under blue light the
599 net kinase activity reduces by more than 1000-fold. The rather stringent response owes to the dual activity
600 of YF1 as a net kinase in darkness and as a net phosphatase under blue light, respectively. The YF1:FixJ TCS
601 achieved the downregulation of a LacZ reporter gene by around 70-fold under blue light in *E. coli* (Möglich et
602 al., 2009). The flavin chromophore of YF1 is generally available in bacterial cells, which contrasts with the PCB
603 chromophore utilized by Cph8 and CcaS (Tabor et al., 2011). Later on, the YF1:FixJ TCS was implemented on
604 the pDusk plasmid that mediated the downregulation of a fluorescent reporter under blue light by around
605 10- to 15-fold (Ohlendorf et al., 2012). The light response of this TCS was inverted within the pDawn plasmid
606 by the same λ cI-based gene cassette that successfully reprogrammed the Cph8:OmpR TCS (Tabor et al.,

607 2011). Triggered by blue light, pDawn prompted an around 450-fold upregulation of expression. More
608 recently, the pDawn system was expanded to the OptoLac setup for metabolic control in bacterial production
609 processes (Lalwani et al., 2021a). In this system, the pDawn circuit was extended by an additional inverter
610 cassette based on the *lac* repressor LacI and its operator *lacO*. As a result, the expression output was
611 repressed by blue light, similar to but more efficient than the original pDusk. The dynamic range of light
612 regulation in OptoLac was boosted to 60-fold by a negative feedback loop, in which LacI not only represses
613 the target gene of interest but also the λ cl repressor (Lalwani et al., 2021a).

614 Analogous to the YF1 design (Möglich et al., 2009), the activity of the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* GacS
615 SHK was put under light control by exchanging its sensor domain for the LOV module from *B. subtilis* YtvA
616 (Cheng et al., 2021). Use of the PATCHY method (Ohlendorf et al., 2016) facilitated the exploration of multiple
617 SHK designs that differed in the length and sequence of the linker between the LOV photosensor and
618 histidine-kinase effector modules. One variant, denoted YGS24, supported blue-light-activated
619 phosphorylation of the GacA RR which, when phosphorylated, prompts the transcription of small regulatory
620 RNAs in *P. aeruginosa* from specific promoters. Using a fluorescent reporter, the YGS24:GacA TCS mediated
621 a 10-fold increase in gene expression from one of these promoters.

622 A widely used system for the optogenetic control of bacterial expression is based on the CBCR CcaS
623 and its cognate RR CcaR which together control chromatic acclimation in *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 (Hirose
624 et al., 2008, 2010; Tabor et al., 2011). Transplanted into *E. coli*, the CcaRS TCS enabled the activation of target
625 gene expression by green light which could be rapidly and completely reverted by ensuing illumination with
626 red light. The initially modest regulatory response to green light of around 6-fold enhanced gene expression
627 was subsequently boosted to more than 100-fold by adjusting the amounts of the TCS components and the
628 promoter sequences, as also done for the Cph8:OmpR TCS (Schmidl et al., 2014; Tabor et al., 2011). An
629 additional improvement of the light response arose from modification of the CcaS receptor itself which
630 features two PAS domains between its CBCR photosensor and histidine-kinase effector modules. Removal of
631 these two PAS domains, which are not known to respond to any signal, not only decreased the size of the
632 resultant SHK, denoted mini-CcaS (Nakajima et al., 2016a), but also it further improved the regulatory
633 response when embedded in a TCS together with CcaR. In the optimized setup (Ong and Tabor, 2018), target-
634 gene expression increased by almost 600-fold under green light relative to darkness or red light. In addition
635 to supporting high dynamic ranges, the CcaRS system offers the advantage of bimodal, photochromic control,
636 see above. As a CBCR, CcaS requires the PCB chromophore which for bacterial expression is routinely
637 provided by HO/PcyA coexpression. Intriguingly, length variations of the linker between the sensor and
638 effector modules in mini-CcaS led to the generation of SHK variants that exhibited the opposite light
639 response, i.e. higher expression under red than under green light, albeit at somewhat reduced efficiency

640 (Nakajima et al., 2016a). These observations resemble earlier findings for YF1, see above (Ohlendorf et al.,
641 2016), and likely reflect SHK signal transduction via α -helical coiled coils (Möglich, 2019; Möglich et al., 2009).

642 As a group, CBCRs offer remarkably diverse color sensitivity, which can be in principle harnessed for
643 bacterial optogenetics. As a case in point, the UirS CBCR SHK and its UirR RR, also from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC
644 6803 (Song et al., 2011), enabled the control of expression in *E. coli* by UV and green light (Ramakrishnan and
645 Tabor, 2016). Irradiation with near-UV light around 380-400 nm engendered up to 6-fold enhanced target-
646 gene expression which could be counteracted by green light. Although the dynamic range of regulation is
647 comparatively low, it is important to note that the initial implementation of the CcaRS TCS showed light
648 responses of similar magnitude (Tabor et al., 2011). Hence, there could be scope for much improving the
649 extent of the UirRS light response along the lines previously successful for other systems (Schmidl et al.,
650 2014).

651 We recently advanced derivatives of the pDusk and pDawn systems, dubbed pREDusk and pREDawn,
652 that react to red and NIR, rather than blue light (Multamäki et al., 2022). To this end, the LOV module within
653 YF1 was substituted for the PCM of the *DrBphP*, thus yielding the new SHK *DrF1*. Interestingly, target gene
654 expression within the pREDusk system was decreased by around 200-fold under red light, thus much
655 surpassing the blue-light response of the original pDusk. By contrast, pREDawn mediated an around 70-fold
656 increase of gene expression under red light, which is somewhat less efficient than the pDawn performance
657 (Ohlendorf et al., 2012). BphPs like *DrF1* require the supply of biliverdin as a chromophore which in pREDusk
658 and pREDawn is ensured via coexpression of the *D. radiodurans* HO from within the same operon as the TCS.

659 Transcriptional repressors

660 A setup based on the bathyphytochrome BphP1 and the transcriptional repressor PpsR2, both from
661 *Rhodospseudomonas palustris* CGA009, also employs two polypeptide components but is distinct from TCSs
662 (Ong et al., 2018). When converted to its Pr state by far-red light, *RpBphP1* heterodimerizes with *RpPpsR2*
663 and thereby impairs repression. The optimization of promoter sequences and expression levels led to an
664 optogenetic system that achieved up to 2.5-fold upregulation of a fluorescent reporter under NIR light
665 compared to red light or darkness. Despite a comparatively low dynamic range of regulation, the
666 *RpBphP1:RpPpsR2* system has the advantage of being activated by NIR light.

667 Compared to the previous systems, a series of setups achieve optogenetic control of bacterial
668 expression by directly, rather than indirectly as in TCSs, controlling the activity of transcriptional activators
669 and repressors. As noted above, these setups generally offer a simpler architecture and smaller genetic
670 footprint than TCSs. Although most pertinent setups achieve optogenetic regulation via light-dependent
671 dimerization and dissociation reactions, the pioneering LOV-TAP system does not but relies on other modes
672 of allostery (Strickland et al., 2008). This system harnesses the widely used AsLOV2 module which undergoes

673 reversible unfolding of its N-terminal A'α and C-terminal Jα helices under blue light (Dietler et al., 2022;
674 Harper et al., 2003; Zayner et al., 2012). Within LOV-TAP, the AsLOV2 domain is fused to the *E. coli* tryptophan
675 repressor (TrpR) such that the Jα helix overlaps in sequence with an N-terminal helix of TrpR. A scenario of
676 mutually exclusive folding/function results, where either AsLOV2 or TrpR, but not both entities, can claim the
677 shared helical segment. In darkness, the helix is predominantly folded onto the AsLOV2 core domain and
678 hence not available to TrpR. Under blue light, the affinity of AsLOV2 for its Jα helix drops, and the TrpR thus
679 claims the shared helix and thereby becomes competent to bind DNA. The initially low blue-light-induced
680 gain in DNA affinity of 6-fold was later improved to around 65-fold by modulating the interface between the
681 AsLOV2 core and the Jα helix (Strickland et al., 2010). Despite these advances, LOV-TAP has seen little use in
682 bacterial optogenetics (Abbondanza et al., 2017), potentially because its overall DNA affinity is much reduced
683 compared to the wild-type TrpR (Strickland et al., 2008, 2010). That notwithstanding, LOV-TAP represents
684 one of the pioneering examples that showcased how LOV domains can serve to regulate the activity of target
685 proteins by light (Lee et al., 2008; Möglich et al., 2009; Strickland et al., 2008; Wu et al., 2009).

686 Building on the LightOn system for blue-light-activated mammalian gene expression (Wang et al.,
687 2012), the LightOff setup mediates blue-light-repressed bacterial expression (Chen et al., 2016) (Fig. 3B). This
688 setup employs the chimeric transcription factor LEVI, which comprises the homodimerizing NcVVD module
689 connected to the C-terminal DNA-binding domain (DBD) of the *E. coli* LexA repressor. LexA is an integral part
690 of the UV-induced SOS stress response and regulates the expression of several target genes in *E. coli* (Wade
691 et al., 2005). As the isolated LexA DBD is monomeric, it shows little affinity for its target operators. Linkage
692 to NcVVD and light-induced assembly restored the homodimeric state of the LexA DBD and DNA binding. In
693 the LightOff system, LEVI achieved pronounced downregulation of a fluorescent reporter by around 10,000-
694 fold under blue light. Remarkably, the reported regulatory effect thus significantly surpassed that for
695 induction by IPTG (β-isopropyl-thiogalactoside) of a T7-*lacO* promoter, even when the T7 lysozyme was
696 included via the pLysS plasmid (Chen et al., 2016; Ohlendorf et al., 2012). Apart from small-scale formats,
697 LEVI also supported light-repressed gene expression at the fermenter scale. LEVI was further combined with
698 a λ ci-based inversion cassette to furnish the LEVlon system which achieved a 500-fold upregulation of
699 expression under blue light.

700 An advantageous property of the dimerization-based optogenetic strategies is their inherent
701 modularity which facilitates the construction of derivative systems with novel properties. This was duly
702 exploited for the development of the eLightOn setup which uses LexRO, a covalent fusion between the LexA
703 DBD and the RsLOV module (Li et al., 2020). In darkness, RsLOV mediated homodimerization of LexRO and
704 repression at target promoters; under blue light, LexRO dissociated into monomers, and the expression of a
705 fluorescent reporter increased by up to around 500-fold. Notably, the LexRO setup utilizes the modified
706 LexA₄₀₈ variant with altered DNA specificity and reduced affinity for the endogenous bacterial LexA-

707 dependent promoters (Thliveris et al., 1991). Use of this variant is thus expected to reduce off-target activity
708 and limit the impact on endogenous pathways. The eLightOn setup enabled the regulation of bacterial
709 motility and cell morphology as a function of blue light. Moreover, the combination of LexRO with the
710 chemically inducible AraC yielded genetic circuits which acted as Boolean logic gates and achieved different
711 outputs depending on the input signals blue light and L-arabinose. Notably, LexRO exhibited robust
712 performance at 37°C which contrasts with a temperature lability of the wild-type *RsLOV* module reported in
713 other studies (Dietler et al., 2021; Richter et al., 2016).

714 Again using the LexA₄₀₈ DBD, a red-light-responsive bacterial gene expression system was established
715 (Kaberniuk et al., 2021). This system harnesses the light-induced oligomerization of a modified PCM from the
716 *Idiomarina* sp. A28L BphP (*IsPCM*) that forms a homodimer in its Pr state but a homotetramer in its Pfr state.
717 Linked to the LexA₄₀₈ DBD, the *IsPCM* afforded the downregulation of a fluorescent reporter by 115-fold
718 under red light, indicating that the chimeric transcription factor is more active in its tetrameric than its
719 dimeric state.

720 The homodimeric Tet repressor (TetR) supports many applications in both prokaryotic and eukaryotic
721 hosts, prominently so within the Tet-ON and Tet-OFF systems (Gossen et al., 1995). Although an early study
722 subjected TetR-based mammalian expression circuits to optogenetic control, it did so by regulating in light-
723 dependent manner the activity of a eukaryotic *trans*-activation domain appended to TetR (Müller et al.,
724 2015). Consequently, the system did not translate to the prokaryotic setting. We recently developed a suite
725 of light-regulated TetR variants based on light-induced homodimer association or dissociation (Dietler et al.,
726 2021). Serial C-terminal truncation impaired TetR dimerization and incurred a loss of repression at target
727 operators. The homodimeric state and repression capability were rescued by C-terminal fusion of different
728 LOV modules. The dissociating *RsLOV* underpins the pLITR system which prompted upregulation of a
729 fluorescent reporter under blue light. While the regulatory efficiency at 29°C amounted to around 40-fold, it
730 plummeted to around 2-fold at 37°C. The poor performance at the higher temperature could be tied to an
731 overall low homodimer affinity in dark-adapted *RsLOV*, see allosteric mechanisms above, and an intrinsic
732 temperature lability. The performance at 37°C could be improved to up to ~ 14-fold dynamic range in two
733 *RsLOV* variants harboring the D109G mutation or a redesigned dimer interface. As these modifications
734 concern the *RsLOV* module itself, the variants could also apply to other setups based on the same LOV
735 module. As a case in point, these variants may benefit the LexRO system (Li et al., 2020), which at least in
736 one instance failed to elicit light-induced expression changes (Wang et al., 2022), potentially due to the
737 temperature lability of *RsLOV*. Owing to the modular design, the *RsLOV* module was easily exchanged for the
738 associating *NcVVD* and *PtLOV* modules (Dietler et al., 2021). In the corresponding pLATR setups, TetR
739 repression was enhanced by blue light, and up to 75-fold reduction of gene expression resulted. In another
740 study, the repression by TetR was subjected to light control by splitting the repressor into two parts (Komera

741 et al., 2022). Linkage of the resultant fragments to *NcVVD* provided the TRU system which mediated the light-
742 induced reconstitution of the repressor and a 13-fold downregulation of a fluorescent reporter. Combination
743 with the LacI repressor generated the inverted TAU circuit in which target gene expression increased by up
744 to 5-fold under blue light.

745 The above light-regulated transcriptional repressors are complemented by the CarH receptor from
746 *Myxococcus xanthus* which in darkness binds as a homotetramer to target operators and thereby blocks
747 expression (Ortiz-Guerrero et al., 2011). Green light drives the irreversible dissociation into CarH monomers
748 which detach from DNA and relieve repression. Using LacZ as a reporter, green light thus elevated gene
749 expression by around 10-fold. As pointed out above, the application of CarH outside its original host is
750 complicated by the requirement for the cobalamin chromophore.

751 Beyond conventional repressors, the RNA-guided DNA endonuclease Cas9 can also mediate
752 transcriptional repression once its catalytic activity has been disrupted by mutagenesis. In the so-called
753 CRISPR interference (CRISPRi) strategy (Gilbert et al., 2013), the cleavage-deficient dCas9 serves as a
754 programmable repressor that can be adapted to near-arbitrary DNA targets via single guide RNAs (gRNA) of
755 matching sequence. This key property was exploited in several studies that regulate the expression of Cas9
756 in light-dependent manner, rather than its activity (Wu et al., 2014, 2021; Zhang and Poh, 2018). Although
757 several directly light-regulated (d)Cas9 variants were developed for mammalian use, they often achieve
758 optogenetic regulation via light-dependent recruitment of transcriptional effector modules but leave
759 sequence-specific DNA binding, central to CRISPRi, unaffected by light. That said, at least certain dCas9
760 variants that are regulated by light-dependent dimerization reactions should also apply to optogenetics in
761 bacteria (Nihongaki et al., 2015; Richter et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2018). Despite the potential of these
762 approaches, they have to date seen little use in bacterial optogenetics and will hence not be treated in detail
763 here.

764 Transcriptional activators

765 In addition to repressors, transcriptional activators were also leveraged for optogenetic expression control
766 in bacteria. The LOV helix-turn-helix (HTH) receptor EL222 from *Erythrobacter litoralis* (Motta-Mena et al.,
767 2014; Nash et al., 2011) that homodimerizes and binds to DNA when activated by blue light underlies several
768 systems (Camsund et al., 2021; Ding et al., 2020; Jayaraman et al., 2016) (Fig. 4B). By placing the EL222 target
769 operator upstream of the -35 promoter region, expression of a fluorescent reporter was ramped up by
770 maximally 5-fold under blue light within the pLind setup (Jayaraman et al., 2016). Within the pLRep setup,
771 said operator was placed between the -10 and -35 regions, and hence blue-light-induced EL222 binding
772 caused a 3-fold reduction of gene expression. The availability of two compact EL222-based setups that elicit
773 opposite outputs in response to light paves the way towards novel applications, as showcased for the light-
774 dependent regulation of communication between bacterial cells (Jayaraman et al., 2016). A later study used

775 a highly similar strategy to obtain the BLAT and BLRT systems for the light-induced 24-fold increase and 53-
776 fold reduction, respectively, of bacterial gene expression (Ding et al., 2020). The better performance of BLAT
777 and BLRT over pBLind and pBLrep owed to optimization of the EL222 expression levels and the sequence of
778 its target operator site.

779 One of the most common systems for chemically inducing bacterial expression employs the L-
780 arabinose (L-Ara)-responsive AraC transcriptional activator and its target P_{BAD} promoter. Removal of the N-
781 terminal dimerization and L-Ara-binding domain of AraC rendered the C-terminal DBD monomeric and largely
782 incapable of activating expression (Romano et al., 2021) (Fig. 4B). Similar to the LightOff setup (Li et al., 2020),
783 the BLADE system restored the homodimeric state of the AraC DBD and transcriptional activation by N-
784 terminal appendage of the NcVVD module (Romano et al., 2021). Effectively, the chimeric AraC-NcVVD
785 transcription factor thus recapitulated the architecture and activation mechanism of the naturally occurring
786 EL222 which also relies on light-activated dimerization (Nash et al., 2011). When exposed to blue light, BLADE
787 triggered the upregulation of fluorescent-reporter expression by up to 15-fold. Commendably, the authors
788 assessed in detail how the light-dependent response of BLADE scales with the expression strength of AraC-
789 NcVVD, that in turn governs its intracellular concentration. As fundamentally expected for setups that
790 activate via dimerization, see Fig. 2B and (Ziegler and Möglich, 2015), the performance of BLADE strongly
791 depended on the AraC-NcVVD levels (Romano et al., 2021). Whereas at intermediate expression levels, a
792 substantial upregulation of expression could be induced by light, at lower or higher levels, the light response
793 was partially or completely degraded. To at least certain extent, similar effects also apply to all other
794 oligomerization-based optogenetic tools, although this aspect has seldom been investigated. With an optimal
795 AraC-NcVVD expression set by suitable constitutive or inducible promoters, robust light responses could be
796 evoked by BLADE while maintaining low leakiness. Given the modular architecture of BLADE, the NcVVD
797 module could be functionally replaced by VfLOV, albeit at lower efficiency. While NcVVD performed better
798 when connected to the N terminus of the AraC DBD, rather than the C terminus, the opposite proved true
799 for VfLOV. These findings arguably reflect the signal transduction mechanisms of these LOV modules which
800 hinge on their N- and C-terminal segments, respectively.

801 Second-messenger signaling

802 Besides the above setups relying on TCSs and oligomerization reactions, a clade of systems achieve light-
803 dependent bacterial expression via second-messenger signaling. Following their initial discovery in protists
804 (Iseki et al., 2002), photoactivated adenylyl cyclases, that produce 3',5'-cyclic adenosine monophosphate
805 when exposed to light, were identified in different organisms (Avelar et al., 2014; Blain-Hartung et al., 2018;
806 Ohki et al., 2017; Raffelberg et al., 2013; Ryu et al., 2010; Stierl et al., 2011) or were obtained by protein
807 engineering (Ettl et al., 2018; Fushimi et al., 2017; Ryu et al., 2014; Stüven et al., 2019) (Fig. 4D). As
808 exemplified for bPAC from *Beggiatoa* sp. (Ryu et al., 2010; Stierl et al., 2011), certain PACs exhibit stringently

809 light-regulated cyclase activity with dynamic ranges of several hundred-fold. PACs can be harnessed for
810 driving bacterial expression by combining them with the endogenous catabolite activator protein which acts
811 as a transcriptional activator when in complex with cAMP. Although strong gene-expression responses can
812 be thus evoked, the application scope of PACs appears limited given that cAMP serves as a general second
813 messenger in many bacteria that triggers pleiotropic endogenous responses. A potential solution to this
814 challenge may be provided by light-activated cyclases that produce 3',5'-cyclic guanosine monophosphate
815 (cGMP) (Etzl et al., 2018) and cGMP-responsive CAP homologs (Roychowdhury et al., 2015). That is because,
816 in contrast to mammalian organisms, most bacteria do not employ cGMP for signal transduction.

817 Apart from cyclic mononucleotides, bacteria also use cyclic dinucleotides for signaling, most
818 prominently 3',5'-cyclic diguanylate. As exemplified by BphG1 from *Rhodobacter sphaeroides*, many
819 bacteriophytochromes naturally regulate the activity of GGDEF effectors that synthesize c-di-GMP (Ryu and
820 Gomelsky, 2014). The exchange of the original GGDEF module of BphG1 for a homolog generated BphS with
821 improved light regulation of c-di-GMP synthesis. When coexpressing BphS with the c-di-GMP-dependent
822 transcriptional activator MrkH from *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, the expression of a LacZ reporter could be
823 enhanced by red light. The inclusion of a constitutively active EAL enzyme, which hydrolyzes c-di-GMP,
824 reduced leakiness and thereby improved the dynamic range of the system to around 40-fold. Later on, the
825 circuit was expanded by the blue-light-activated BLUF-EAL phosphodiesterase BlrP1 from *K. pneumoniae*
826 (Huang et al., 2018), thereby enabling bimodal control of c-di-GMP synthesis and hydrolysis by red and blue
827 light, respectively. Optogenetic circuits relying on light-dependent c-di-GMP production may further benefit
828 from more recently engineered BphP-GGDEF variants that are regulated in their activity by up to 800-fold by
829 red light (Gourinchas et al., 2019). As discussed for cAMP, c-di-GMP also triggers a raft of endogenous
830 pathways, not least prompting the formation of biofilms in many bacterial species. Unless biofilm formation
831 and other c-di-GMP-dependent processes are specifically demanded (Huang et al., 2018), the application of
832 BphS to regulating bacterial gene expression may be restricted.

833 Optoribogenetic control at the mRNA level

834 Whereas the above approaches regulate bacterial gene expression at the DNA level, several optoribogenetic
835 setups operate at the mRNA level (mechanism 5 in Fig. 3). The first of these systems employs the LOV
836 photoreceptor PAL from *Nakamurella multipartita* (Weber et al., 2019) which comprises a sequence-specific
837 RNA-binding ANTAR effector (Shu and Zhulin, 2002). In darkness, the ANTAR moiety of PAL is in tight complex
838 with a LOV module and thus autoinhibited. Blue light relieves the intramolecular inhibition and thereby
839 increases the affinity of PAL for specific RNA hairpins, denoted aptamers in the following, by 100-fold to
840 between 5 and 20 nM, depending on RNA sequence (Ranzani et al., 2022; Weber et al., 2019). The sequence-
841 specific, light-activated RNA binding of PAL was leveraged for the regulation of bacterial expression by
842 interleaving the aptamer with the Shine-Dalgarno (SD) sequence of a target gene (Fig. 4E). Once activated by

843 light, PAL could then bind to this region of the mRNA and thereby interfere with translation, which led to an
844 up to 10-fold reduction of fluorescent reporter expression at 29°C (Weber et al., 2019). To facilitate the
845 adoption of PAL-based optoribogenetic circuits, we recently developed the pCrepusculo system which is
846 realized on a single plasmid and implements an improved aptamer sequence with higher affinity for PAL
847 (Ranzani et al., 2022). pCrepusculo enabled the 8-fold downregulation of expression at 37°C. As for several
848 of the transcription-based optogenetic approaches (Ohlendorf et al., 2012; Tabor et al., 2011), introduction
849 of a λ cl repressor cassette inverted the response to light, and the resulting pAurora system prompted 67-
850 fold increased gene expression under blue light (Ranzani et al., 2022). We recently also harnessed the light-
851 induced PAL:aptamer interaction to repress by blue light the autocatalytic cleavage of a modified
852 hammerhead ribozyme (HHR) (Pietruschka et al., 2022). By embedding the HHR in the 5'-untranslated region
853 (UTR) of an mRNA, its SD sequence was masked, and expression thus attenuated. In darkness, the HHR can
854 cleave itself and thereby expose the SD region, allowing translation to ensue. Light-induced binding of PAL
855 to the modified HHR interfered with ribozyme cleavage and therefore led to an around 3-fold repression of
856 bacterial expression under blue light. Although this optoribogenetic strategy currently has comparatively low
857 regulatory efficiency, it hints at the versatility of light-dependent protein:RNA interactions. While the natural
858 targets of PAL in *N. multipartita* have not been identified yet, it appears likely that the light-dependent
859 regulation involves a transcriptional anti-termination mechanism, where binding of the ANTAR protein to the
860 nascent mRNA disrupts an intrinsic terminator sequence (Wilson et al., 1993). By that token, PAL can
861 presumably support yet other modes of optoribogenetic regulation at the mRNA level.

862 The more recent LicV setup indeed employs transcriptional antitermination and thereby upregulates
863 bacterial gene expression by around 17-fold under blue light (Liu et al., 2022). LicV is based on the co-
864 antitermination (CAT) domain of *B. subtilis* LicT which is monomeric in isolation and hence little active.
865 Connection to a C-terminal NcVVD module enabled light-induced homodimerization, followed by CAT binding
866 to the target RAT motif in the nascent mRNA and antitermination. The affinity of LicV for its target RAT motif
867 amounted to 90 nM in blue light and around 3.8 μ M in darkness, corresponding to an around 42-fold-
868 difference. Compared to PAL, the binding of LicV to its RNA is thus weaker and less strongly regulated by blue
869 light (Ranzani et al., 2022; Weber et al., 2019).

870 The optoribogenetic regulation of bacterial expression has several traits that may prove advantageous
871 to application. First, as the light-dependent regulation is exerted at the mRNA level, the corresponding setups
872 lend themselves to combinations with circuits, optogenetic or otherwise, that act at the DNA level (Ranzani
873 et al., 2022). Doing so may give rise to integrated circuits with finer-grained and more pronounced light
874 responses, which potentially benefit optogenetic applications, for example in bioproduction processes, see
875 below. Second, as not least illustrated by the highly versatile bacterial riboswitches (Breaker, 2018), signal-
876 dependent RNA interactions can be leveraged in multiple ways for expression control. For example, the

877 stability of certain mRNAs in *E. coli* and hence the expression of proteins encoded by them is regulated by
878 binding of proteins to cognate RNA motifs within the 3'-UTR (Tang and Guest, 1999). Although not realized
879 yet, integrating the RNA aptamers recognized by PAL and LicV into these motifs may render mRNA stability
880 and gene expression light-dependent.

881 Posttranslational optogenetic control

882 The steady-state intracellular activity and concentration of target proteins may also be optogenetically
883 regulated after translation is completed. While versatile optogenetic strategies now allow the direct allosteric
884 light-dependent control of various proteins (Dagliyan et al., 2016; Losi et al., 2018), they are often particular
885 to the protein in question and require its covalent modification with light-sensitive photoreceptor modules.
886 In this treatise, we will hence not consider these specific strategies, but rather focus on generic approaches
887 that apply to various targets with minimal adaptation necessary. As one example, several optogenetic
888 strategies modulate protein activity via light-dependent sequestration into clusters or complexes. For
889 instance, two approaches based on plant cryptochromes and cyanobacterial BLUF receptors, respectively,
890 enable the formation or dissolution of protein clusters and RNA-dependent liquid-liquid phase separation
891 (LLPS) upon illumination (Dine et al., 2018; Shin et al., 2017) (mechanism ⑥ in Fig. 3). Ligation with
892 photoreceptor modules engaged in clustering allows the light-dependent removal of target proteins from
893 the regular cytosolic pool and their sequestration into the separated liquid phases. Inside these membrane-
894 less organelles, the activity of the protein of interest may be lowered. Alternatively, enzymes may thus be
895 colocalized, and metabolic flux increases, as demonstrated in yeast (Zhao et al., 2019). Several recently
896 developed classes of light-activated nanobodies and monobodies may find similar application for the
897 sequestration and colocalization of target proteins (Carrasco-López et al., 2020; Gil et al., 2020; He et al.,
898 2021; Reis et al., 2018; Woloschuk et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2019a). Moreover, light-activated binding to the
899 protein of interest may directly reduce its activity.

900 Finally, the intracellular lifetime of target proteins can be optogenetically controlled (mechanism ⑦
901 in Fig. 3). Corresponding strategies are well established in eukaryotes (Bonger et al., 2014; Renicke et al.,
902 2013) and involve the light-controlled unmasking of a degron signal which then prompts protein degradation
903 via the ubiquitin-proteasome system. By contrast, optogenetic strategies for the deliberate, light-induced
904 degradation of target proteins in bacteria are scarce. In *E. coli*, truncated proteins arising from incomplete
905 translation are marked by a C-terminal peptide tag that is encoded by the *ssrA* transfer-messenger RNA.
906 Proteins are thus designated for degradation by the ClpAPX protease. This principle has long been exploited
907 to control the persistence of proteins inside bacteria (Andersen et al., 1998). The intracellular lifetime can be
908 greatly modulated by appending to target proteins different variants of the *ssrA* peptide tag, with the three
909 most C-terminal residues being particularly important. Interestingly, one of the most widely used setups for
910 light-induced protein:protein interactions, the iLID system (Guntas et al., 2015), employs a modified *ssrA*

911 peptide that lacks these three C-terminal residues. It has however not been reported if or to what extent iLID
912 can be reconfigured for inducing protein degradation by light in bacteria. Against this backdrop, the PRU
913 approach pursues a different strategy based on split TEV protease and the *NcVVD* module (Komera et al.,
914 2022). Blue light prompted reconstitution of the TEV protease and enabled the on-demand cleavage of target
915 proteins. When the specific TEV target epitope was incorporated into a fluorescent reporter, blue light
916 triggered a 12-fold reduction in fluorescence. The response to light could be inverted by appending to the C-
917 terminus of target proteins a *ssrA* peptide tag via a linker containing a TEV target site. In this manner, the
918 split TEV protease cleaved off the tag under blue light, the degradation via the ClpAPX system was reduced,
919 and the reporter fluorescence increased 4-fold.

920 Multiplexed control of bacterial expression

921 The cohort of available optogenetic tools, summarized above, also support multiplexed control of gene
922 expression by several stimuli rather than a single light color. For an in-depth overview on multiplexed
923 optogenetic circuits, we refer to (Dwijayanti et al., 2022). Multiplexing can potentially provide more stringent
924 light-dependent regulation and better resolution of gene expression in time and space (Ziegler and Möglich,
925 2015). While not relevant for every single of the applications detailed below, certain use cases of light-
926 regulated bacterial gene expression could benefit from these aspects. The arguably most straight-forward
927 option for implementing multiplexed optogenetic control uses photochromic photoreceptors, particularly
928 those of the phytochrome superfamily, that are inherently sensitive to two light colors. As noted above, in
929 these photoreceptors not only the population of the signaling state is light-driven, but also its depletion is.
930 The reversion to the resting state can thus be much accelerated compared to non-photochromic receptors
931 which feature slow, thermal recovery reactions (Fig. 2E, F). The bidirectional switching afforded by
932 photochromic photoreceptors thus enables superior temporal precision and allows gene expression to be
933 toggled on and off at will, even repeatedly. Beyond photochromic systems, certain photoreceptors combine
934 multiple photosensor modules into a single polypeptide, arguably to sense and integrate several light stimuli.
935 Apart from the well-known neochromes (Nozue et al., 1998) and *Rhodospirillum centenum* Ppr (Jiang et al.,
936 1999), neither of which (yet) appears to immediately apply to the optogenetic expression control in bacteria,
937 it is foremost the CBCR receptors that are relevant. These receptors often comprise arrays of precisely spaced
938 CBCR modules that individually respond to distinct light colors (Fushimi and Narikawa, 2019; Rockwell et al.,
939 2013). Likely, composite CBCR receptors register several light cues and compute a joint output signal.
940 Receptors that comprise several sensor domains and integrate (light) stimuli can also be engineered, as
941 exemplified for SHKs that respond to both light and oxygen levels (Möglich et al., 2010).

942 As an alternative to photochromic and multi-sensor receptors, certain photoreceptors and derived
943 circuits are either inherently sensitive to other signals besides light or can be configured thus. With such

944 setups, gene expression may be controlled more precisely than possible for simpler circuits that obey one
945 signal only (Fig. 2E, F). To this end, several studies combined optogenetic circuitry with chemically inducible
946 transcription factors, e.g., LacI or AraC, (Jayaraman et al., 2018b; Li et al., 2020), to construct Boolean logic
947 gates that controlled gene expression jointly by light and chemicals. In a similar vein, the BLADE approach
948 subjected the activity of the AraC DNA-binding and activation domain to optogenetic control (Romano et al.,
949 2021). When combining BLADE with the wild-type AraC, target genes could be induced by either blue light or
950 L-arabinose. Moreover, certain photoreceptors are sensitive to small ligands in addition to light. As the
951 above-described pLITR and pLATR systems retain the ligand-binding portion of the parental TetR, they can
952 be toggled not only by light but also by tetracycline analogs, which could be harnessed for fine-grained gene-
953 expression control (Dietler et al., 2021). For instance, repression within the pLATR setup might first be
954 activated by blue light, hence leading to reduced gene expression; subsequent addition of anhydrotetracyclin
955 would prompt repressor dissociation and restoration of gene expression. Such a setup could be expanded
956 even further as tetracycline is inherently light-sensitive which was exploited for the (non-optogenetic) light-
957 dependent control of bacterial expression (Baumschlager et al., 2020). Moreover, certain pLITR variants
958 based on wild-type *RsLOV* are labile to temperature increases which could potentially be leveraged for
959 multiplexed control of gene expression by light and temperature (Dietler et al., 2021). Although the
960 integration of light signals with other chemical and physical cues can offer certain benefits, there are also
961 limitations to these approaches. Given that systems like the above depart from purely light-dependent
962 control, the desirable traits of optogenetics, such as reversibility, spatiotemporal precision, and non-
963 invasiveness, may be degraded.

964 Multiplexed control can also rely on combinations of several optogenetic tools for bacterial expression.
965 Depending on application, the tools might either be used in parallel in unmodified form, or they may be
966 integrated into joint circuits. As an example of the former, EL222 can serve as either an activator or a
967 repressor, and at different promoters, gene expression can be thus either up- or downregulated by blue light
968 (Ding et al., 2020; Jayaraman et al., 2016). The latter approach appears most straight-forward for pairs of
969 optogenetic implements that act at distinct levels of the gene-expression trajectory, for example at the DNA
970 and mRNA levels, respectively (Ranzani et al., 2022). When multiple photoreceptors are used in concert
971 within the same bacterium or within co-cultures of different bacteria, it is desirable to toggle them by light
972 independently from another. Several options are available to this end, with the most obvious being the use
973 of photoreceptor pairs that are sensitive to different light colors. For instance, one of the many blue-light-
974 sensitive setups may be combined with the CcaRS system (Fernandez-Rodriguez et al., 2017). As is apparent
975 from the absorbance spectra of CcaR in its Pg and Pr states (Fig. 1B), to some extent this photoreceptor also
976 absorbs blue light which may principally trigger its interconversion. However, even if inadvertent activation
977 by blue light occurred, subsequent irradiation with red and green light could counteract this effect.
978 Moreover, we recently demonstrated that the pREDusk and pREDawn platforms, that are based on a BphP,

979 are readily switched by red light but relatively insensitive to comparable intensities of blue light (Multamäki
980 et al., 2022).

981 By contrast, if two photoreceptors respond to the same light bands, e.g., pairs of LOV receptors, they
982 cannot be spectrally separated. However, even then the individual receptors may still be sequentially
983 addressed if they sufficiently differ in their light sensitivity. At low light doses, only the more sensitive circuit
984 would be triggered by light, before at higher light doses the second circuit kicks in as well. Given the
985 hyperbolic dose-activation profiles that many photoreceptor circuits exhibit, see above, the full separation
986 of two systems in this manner may however be difficult (Hennemann et al., 2018; Ziegler and Möglich, 2015)
987 (Fig. 2A). Separation becomes easier for optogenetic circuits that respond to light cooperatively. The
988 resultant sigmoidal activation profiles may be more easily separated in the intensity regime (Fig. 2A).
989 Alternatively, two optogenetic circuits may be sequentially toggled if they have sufficiently different recovery
990 time courses after triggering by light (Hennemann et al., 2018) (Fig. 2C, D). In that scenario, the circuits can
991 be sequentially addressed as they react differentially to trains of light pulses of suitable temporal spacing.
992 The circuit with the faster recovery reaction dwells for less time in the signaling state than the other circuit
993 before reverting to its resting state. Put another way, all other parameters being equal, the circuit with the
994 slower recovery is activated to larger extent than the one with the faster reversion. Based on this principle,
995 two variants of the pDawn circuit that differed in their dark-recovery kinetics could be toggled sequentially
996 by blue light (Hennemann et al., 2018).

997 Not only multiplexed approaches, but also other optogenetic applications benefit from the online
998 monitoring of the system under study, for instance via continuous measurements of reporter fluorescence
999 or cell density. Such information can be used to infer the current state of the optogenetic circuit(s) and to
1000 suitably adapt the light intensity (or, color) to maintain or alter the system state as demanded by application.
1001 These approaches are particularly effective for photochromic receptors as their activity state can be
1002 bidirectionally changed by different light colors, as demonstrated for the widely used CcaRS TCS (Davidson
1003 et al., 2013; Miliadis-Argeitis et al., 2016; Steel et al., 2020). However, in principle other optogenetic circuits
1004 may also be controlled in feedback manner, as recently shown for pDusk, pDawn (Datta et al., 2022), and
1005 light-responsive T7RNAP (Gutiérrez Mena et al., 2022).

1006 Applications of optogenetic expression control in bacteria

1007 The past years have seen a growing number of studies capitalize on the above optogenetic tools and regulate
1008 bacterial expression by light (Fig. 5). Whereas the initial implementation and subsequent deployment of most
1009 tools were in *E. coli* laboratory strains, increasingly applications address other bacteria, too. These reports
1010 suggest that at least to some extent the pertinent optogenetic circuits generally apply and translate to other
1011 microorganisms. Beyond *E. coli*, the widely used CcaRS TCS (Tabor et al., 2011) enabled light-regulated gene

1012 expression in *Synechocystis* cyanobacteria (Abe et al., 2014; Badary et al., 2015; Miyake et al., 2014) and *P.*
1013 *aeruginosa* (Hueso-Gil et al., 2020). Likewise, the pDawn setup (Ohlendorf et al., 2012) underpinned
1014 applications in the probiotic *E. coli* Nissle 1917 strain (Alizadeh et al., 2020; Cui et al., 2021; Magaraci et al.,
1015 2014), *P. aeruginosa* (Pu et al., 2018), the marine bacterium *Vibrio natriegens* (Tschirhart et al., 2019; Wang
1016 et al., 2020), and *Shewanella oneidensis* (Zhao et al., 2022). Similarly, EL222 was used in *Sinorhizobium*
1017 *meliloti* (Pirhanov et al., 2021). Applications of none of these three optogenetic circuits are restricted to gram-
1018 negative bacteria but extend to for instance bacilli, e.g., *B. subtilis* (Castillo-Hair et al., 2019), and *Lactococcus*
1019 *lactis* (Pan et al., 2021, 2022; Zhang et al., 2021). While in most of these studies the optogenetic setups were
1020 used essentially unmodified, other reports required the optimization of plasmid backbones, promoters,
1021 ribosome-binding sites, and chromophore supply to elicit and boost light-dependent gene-expression
1022 responses (Castillo-Hair et al., 2019; Hueso-Gil et al., 2020).

1023 We loosely assign the increasingly diverse studies that employ light-regulated bacterial expression to
1024 four application categories: photosensing; bioproduction (Fig. 5A); theranostics (Fig. 5B); photography and
1025 templated materials (Fig. 5C). We note that the individual categories are not mutually exclusive, with certain
1026 studies falling into more than one. As discussed in the following, the individual application categories
1027 capitalize on the benefits of optogenetic regulation in different fashion and degree.

1028 Photosensing

1029 Applications within this heterogenous group harness light-regulated gene expression for controlling bacterial
1030 physiology or for biosensing. These applications therefore primarily exploit the temporal dimension of
1031 optogenetics, while the spatial resolution and reversibility are of subordinate significance. For instance, to
1032 showcase the utility of LexRO (Li et al., 2020) and BLADE (Romano et al., 2021), respectively, both setups
1033 were deployed to render the expression of FtsZ blue-light-dependent and to thus achieve control of bacterial
1034 cell division. In a similar vein, LexRO served to regulate CheZ expression and to thereby modulate bacterial
1035 chemotaxis (Li et al., 2020).

1036 Beyond proof-of-principle demonstrations, the CcaRS TCS enabled the optogenetic control of
1037 asymmetric cell division in *E. coli* (Mushnikov et al., 2019). Under green light, the bacteria expressed a fusion
1038 protein encompassing a c-di-GMP-degrading phosphodiesterase and the scaffold protein PopZ from
1039 *Caulobacter crescentus*. Notably, PopZ spontaneously concentrates in one cell pole within the heterologous
1040 *E. coli*, and the linked phosphodiesterase hence depleted c-di-GMP levels predominantly at this pole. Upon
1041 cell division, two daughter cells with different c-di-GMP concentrations arose. The unequal second-messenger
1042 concentrations in turn ushered in distinct downstream responses in the cells. The optogenetic regulation of
1043 engineered asymmetric cell division will not only facilitate mechanistic research but may also be relevant for

1044 biotechnology. For instance, the light-induced formation of cell progeny specializing on different aspects of
1045 a joint bioproduction chain could benefit multi-stage bioproduction processes (Mushnikov et al., 2019).

1046 Apart from its use in basic research, light-regulated gene expression also supported innovative
1047 applications for biosensing in bacteria. In the SCRIBE system for cellular memory (Farzadfard and Lu, 2014),
1048 suitably configured *E. coli* bacteria “remembered” the exposure to external stimuli. To this end, the bacteria
1049 expressed the β recombinase from the λ phage in combination with a so-called retron cassette. This retron
1050 relies on a bacterial reverse transcriptase to achieve the *in situ* production of single-stranded DNA (ssDNA)
1051 oligonucleotides. In concert with the β recombinase, these oligonucleotides prompt the introduction of
1052 mutations at the site(s) specified by the ssDNA. The pDawn circuit was used to control the expression of a
1053 retron cassette directed against a deliberately incapacitated kanamycin resistance marker. Light-induced
1054 retron action thus eventually restored the resistance marker, which in turn could be quantified at the
1055 population level by antibiotics selection. Taken together, SCRIBE thus enabled the detection of blue-light
1056 stimuli with persistent memory.

1057 A similar concept was pursued in the CAMERA approach (Tang and Liu, 2018). Among other strategies
1058 advanced in this study, the cleavage-deficient dCas9 was connected to a base-editing enzyme (BE) that
1059 promoted the introduction of mutations at target sites specified by gRNAs. Again, pDawn was used for
1060 controlling the expression of the dCas9-BE. Across a bacterial population, blue-light exposure thus gradually
1061 translated into persistent changes of genomic DNA sequence which could be captured by sequencing. The
1062 response at the DNA sequence level scaled with the extent of blue-light application, and the CAMERA
1063 approach could thus be used to count illumination events. Intriguingly, the setup achieved quantifiable light-
1064 dependent responses even if only ten bacteria were sequence-analyzed.

1065 Bioproduction and metabolic engineering

1066 The common denominator of applications within this large group is the light-dependent regulation of
1067 bacterial expression for bioproduction purposes (Hoffman et al., 2022; Montañó López et al., 2022). In the
1068 simplest case, the desired product is a protein or peptide, and its expression can then be directly controlled
1069 by light (Fig. 5A). However, the basic approach also lends itself to the precise modulation of metabolic
1070 production processes that generate desired low-molecular-weight compounds. Irrespective of the specific
1071 scenario, applications within this group usually harness the temporal control, noninvasiveness, and
1072 reversibility afforded by optogenetics, whereas the spatial definition is often little or not important.

1073 The original implementation and quantitative characterization of the available optogenetic circuits
1074 generally entailed the light-dependent expression of reporter genes, particularly fluorescent proteins (see
1075 Table 1). By that token, all these optogenetic systems are principally suited to controlling the production of
1076 target proteins, if by different regulatory mechanisms and with different effectiveness. Beyond small-scale

1077 expression, the original reports on certain optogenetic circuits also demonstrated the feasibility of light-
1078 regulated heterologous gene expression at the preparative and fermenter scales (Chen et al., 2016; Lalwani
1079 et al., 2021a; Ohlendorf et al., 2012). Although these experiments again involved reporter genes to aid
1080 detection and quantification, the optogenetic expression control clearly extends to near-arbitrary target
1081 proteins. This notion is borne out in several studies that used the pDusk/pDawn (Chang et al., 2017; Wu et
1082 al., 2014) and LEVI systems (Yu et al., 2019b) to regulate by light the production of enzymes in *E. coli*. Light-
1083 controlled gene expression was also extended to *in vitro* expression systems (Jayaraman et al., 2018a; Zhang
1084 et al., 2020b). In one study, purified EL222 and a DNA template, based on the pBLind system and encoding a
1085 red-fluorescent protein, were added to cell lysate for *in vitro* protein expression. Blue light induced an up to
1086 10-fold increased fluorescence readout. When EL222 was encoded on the same DNA template, rather than
1087 added as purified protein, the dynamic range degraded to about 3-fold. Another study implemented the
1088 YF1:FixJ TCS to downregulate target genes by blue light in a cell-free system (Zhang et al., 2020b); an inverter
1089 cassette based on the λ phage *ci* repressor achieved upregulation of expression by blue light. By expressing
1090 YF1 and FixJ individually in separate lysates, their ratios could be varied and thus optimized. Doing so
1091 culminated in the blue-light-mediated downregulation and upregulation of fluorescent reporters by
1092 maximally 6-fold and 3.5-fold, respectively. As noted by the authors, these systems may not only be
1093 interesting for *in vitro* protein production *per se* but also for engineering artificial cell-free systems with
1094 signaling capability.

1095 Beyond macromolecular protein targets, many studies using light-regulated bacterial expression aim
1096 at optimizing the bioproduction yields of small metabolites and compounds. As a general strategy, such
1097 compounds may be synthesized by diverting intermediates from the cellular metabolism towards enzymatic
1098 pathways leading to the desired substance, as demonstrated in pioneering work in baker's yeast (Zhao et al.,
1099 2018). In the pertinent studies, the redirection of metabolic flux is mostly achieved by optogenetically
1100 regulating the expression of key enzymes catalyzing chemical conversions at metabolic branchpoints.
1101 Reaction pathways are thus opened up or shut down in light-dependent manner. In a comparatively simple
1102 implementation of this concept (Wang et al., 2020), the pDawn circuit drove the expression of a tyrosinase
1103 in the fast-growing marine bacterium *V. natriegens* under blue light. The tyrosinase catalyzed the oxidation
1104 of tyrosine to *ortho*-dihydroxyphenylalanine (Dopa) and dopaquinone which in turn polymerized to the
1105 photoprotective melanin pigment. The optogenetic circuit thus installed temporal control of melanin
1106 pigment formation which may benefit industrial processes, according to the authors.

1107 Two studies leveraged the CcaRS TCS to redirect the metabolic flux of glycolysis intermediates in *E. coli*
1108 (Senoo et al., 2019; Tandar et al., 2019). In one study (Tandar et al., 2019), the expression of glucose-6-
1109 phosphate (G6P) isomerase (GPI) was placed under CcaRS optogenetic control in a *gpi* knockout strain. Green
1110 light activated GPI expression and mediated isomerization of G6P to fructose-6-phosphate, thus allowing its

1111 further metabolization to pyruvate. By contrast, red light lowered GPI expression, and G6P was thus
1112 metabolized to bigger extent via the pentose-phosphate pathway that generates reduction equivalents in
1113 the form of NADPH. As bioproduction processes often involve the reduction of precursors to less oxidized,
1114 desired reaction products, the optogenetically controlled switch between glycolysis and pentose-phosphate
1115 pathway may prove widely useful. A second report targeted a step further downstream in glycolysis, namely
1116 the reversible interconversion of dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP) and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate
1117 (GAP), as catalyzed by triose-phosphate isomerase (TIM) (Senoo et al., 2019). When put under CcaRS control
1118 in a *tim* knockout background, TIM expression was turned on by green light, and glycolysis proceeded.
1119 Exposure to red light reduced TIM expression and hence caused DHAP accumulation as its isomerization to
1120 GAP was hampered. Under these conditions, DHAP was converted to pyruvate via the methylglyoxal (MGO)
1121 pathway, thus incurring increased levels of the eponymous MGO. Given that elevated MGO levels are
1122 cytotoxic, the authors argued that this mode of metabolic rewiring may be used for restricting growth and
1123 cell division in bioproduction processes, also see below.

1124 A recent report combined the CcaRS and YF1:FixJ TCSs to shuttle metabolic flux between the
1125 tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCC) and production of polyhydroxybutyrate, a biodegradable polymer (Wang et al.,
1126 2022). To this end, the CcaRS system controlled the expression of citrate synthase (*gltA*) which is responsible
1127 for importing acetyl-CoA into the TCC. The light response of the YF1:FixJ TCS was inverted using a gene
1128 cassette based on the PhIF repressor (Stanton et al., 2014) and controlled the *phbABC* gene cluster that
1129 mediates PHB biosynthesis starting from acetyl-CoA. As the two optogenetic circuits respond to different
1130 light colors, the expression of the target genes could be controlled individually and thereby synchronized in
1131 time. The maximal PHB yield resulted when cultures were first grown in green light (i.e. expression of *gltA*
1132 but not *phbABC*), followed by sequential illumination with blue light (to activate *phbABC* expression), and
1133 replacement of green by red light (to shut off *gltA* expression).

1134 The OptoLAC circuit, described above, was conceived for optogenetically regulating bioproduction
1135 processes in *E. coli* (Lalwani et al., 2021a). On the one hand, OptoLAC served to control the expression of a
1136 three-gene pathway that mediates the conversion of acetyl-CoA to mevalonate, an isoprene precursor.
1137 Bacteria harboring this system were first cultivated under blue light, thus shutting off target-gene expression.
1138 At a certain optical density, the cultures were transferred to darkness which prompted the gradual induction
1139 of expression and mevalonate production. Upon optimizing the timing of optogenetic induction control,
1140 mevalonate titers could be achieved that exceeded those obtained for chemical induction by around a
1141 quarter. In another application, OptoLAC controlled the expression of five genes that jointly catalyze the
1142 conversion of pyruvate to isobutanol. As before, bacterial cultures were first grown under blue light before
1143 transfer to darkness. Doing so led to maximal isobutanol yields that again were a quarter higher than when
1144 using chemical induction. A recent study (Cheng et al., 2022) employed OptoLAC to modulate the expression

1145 of a modified variant of fatty-acid photodecarboxylase from *Chlorella variabilis* (CvFAP) (Sorigué et al., 2017).
1146 Notably, CvFAP and its variants serve as photoenzymes that catalyze the blue-light-driven decarboxylation of
1147 fatty acids, α -hydroxy carboxylic acids, and α -amino acids. Owing to its stereospecificity, the CvFAP variant
1148 can specifically decarboxylate the D isomer of phosphinothricin (PPT), thus enabling the production of the L
1149 isomer starting from a racemic D/L mixture. Cultivation under intermittent blue-light illumination toggled *E.*
1150 *coli* bacteria harboring OptoLAC-controlled CvFAP between expression of the photoenzyme (darkness) and
1151 photocatalysis (blue light). Using this strategy, L-PPT was obtained in a one-pot reaction with better yield and
1152 enantiomeric excess than when illumination was continuous.

1153 At least certain of the above examples required knockout bacterial strains to redirect metabolic flux.
1154 As demonstrated for the production of muconic acid, a precursor for chemical synthesis, the combination of
1155 optogenetic expression control and CRISPRi can potentially obviate this requirement (Wu et al., 2021). The
1156 EL222 circuit controlled the expression of cleavage-deficient dCpf1 and an associated array of gRNAs, thus
1157 enabling the knockdown of target genes upon blue-light exposure. With this strategy, several metabolic
1158 pathways that consume phosphoenol pyruvate could be inhibited, and metabolic flux could be diverted from
1159 the biosynthesis of aromatic amino acids to that of muconic acid. In addition to enabling the expression
1160 control of genomically encoded genes, rather than plasmid-borne ones, the CRISPRi strategy offers the
1161 advantage of hitting several targets simultaneously via different gRNAs.

1162 Bioproduction processes and yields can also be enhanced by optogenetically controlling bacterial
1163 proliferation (Ding et al., 2020). To this end, one report combined the EL222-based BLAT and BLRT setups
1164 with a BphS-dependent, red-light-responsive circuit, denoted NRAT, to manipulate the timing and duration
1165 of bacterial DNA replication and cell division. Whereas the light-gated expression of ribonucleotide reductase
1166 promoted DNA synthesis, expressing FtsA and FtsZ accelerated cell division. Optogenetically regulating these
1167 and several other genes allowed the proliferation speed of *E. coli* to be set. By shortening the time taken for
1168 cell division, the production yield of the food flavor acetoin was improved. Contrarily, the optogenetically
1169 induced lengthening of cell division improved the yields of the biodegradable polymer poly-(lactate-co-3-
1170 hydroxybutyrate).

1171 Certain bioproduction processes may benefit from co-culturing different microorganisms that jointly
1172 synthesize the compound of interest by “division of labor” (Lalwani et al., 2021b). Although desirable, the
1173 stable maintenance of microbial consortia over time is demanding, as one microorganism may outgrow other
1174 ones in the system. To address this challenge, the OptoTA setup harnessed the pDusk and pDawn circuits to
1175 antagonistically express the toxin-antitoxin MazF:MazE pair. *E. coli* cells equipped with OptoTA were
1176 hampered in their growth in darkness owing to MazF expression. Blue light repressed MazF expression,
1177 instead induced expression of the MazE antitoxin, and in sum thus promoted bacterial proliferation. In this
1178 way, *E. coli* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* could be co-cultured at desired titers which enhanced the

1179 bioproduction yields of isobutyl acetate (used as a solvent and potential biofuel) and naringenin (e.g., used
1180 as an antibiotic) (Lalwani et al., 2021b). Other means of optogenetically controlling bacterial viability and
1181 proliferation may also apply to microbial co-cultures. First, the above-described rewiring of glycolysis
1182 increased the levels of the cytotoxic MGO which may reduce cell viability and proliferation (Tandar et al.,
1183 2019). Second, the pDusk setup was used to express the phage-21-derived lysin and to thereby hamper cell
1184 proliferation in darkness. Blue light shut off lysin expression and thus accelerated proliferation (Wang et al.,
1185 2018a). Third, a recent study detailed the application of OptoCreVvd to control the expression of antibiotic
1186 resistance genes by blue light (Sheets and Dunlop, 2022). Following light-induced DNA recombination, *E. coli*
1187 bacteria withstood antibiotics treatment which could prospectively represent a means of controlling cell
1188 titers in bioproduction processes.

1189 Theranostics and towards biomedical applications

1190 Applications within this category have in common that they harness light-regulated bacterial expression in
1191 diagnostic and therapeutic settings. The studies in question rely on the non-invasiveness and temporal
1192 precision afforded by optogenetics, whereas the reversibility and spatial precision of expression play minor
1193 roles to date. The non-invasiveness is especially important for use cases that envision or even realize the
1194 deployment of light-responsive bacteria inside the body of animals, e.g., within their digestive tract (Fig. 5B).
1195 As discussed above, the *in situ* light delivery for triggering the underlying optogenetic circuits may become
1196 limiting in such applications.

1197 Various bacteria produce peptide- or protein-based cytotoxins capable of killing mammalian cells. By
1198 subjecting toxin expression to optogenetic control, bacteria may hence serve as light-responsive agents for
1199 the targeted destruction of mammalian cells, which could prospectively apply to cancer therapy. One early
1200 approach used the pDawn circuit in *E. coli* Nissle 1917 to express cytolysin A, a cytotoxin made by different
1201 *Enterobacteria* (Magaraci et al., 2014). When exposed to blue light, the bacteria responded by cytolysin
1202 production which caused the lysis of red blood cells in blood agar. By contrast, no cytolysis occurred when
1203 bacteria were incubated in darkness. A later study pursued a similar strategy and employed pDawn in *E. coli*
1204 Nissle to drive the expression of α -hemolysin from *Staphylococcus aureus* (Alizadeh et al., 2020). Blue light
1205 promoted toxin production and elicited cell lysis on blood agar, whereas in darkness little or no lysis
1206 happened. The supernatant of bacterial cultures incubated under blue light triggered apoptosis in colon
1207 carcinoma cells, whereas the supernatant of dark-incubated bacteria showed lower propensity for doing so.
1208 Although the path towards eventual application will doubtless be long and arduous, therapeutic settings may
1209 benefit from the ability to govern cell killing with precise timing, dosing, and spatial control, as enabled by
1210 the optogenetic circuits.

1211 Another study used optogenetics to control by light the virulence of *P. aeruginosa* via the YGS24:GacA
1212 TCS (Cheng et al., 2021). Blue light promoted the transcription of two endogenous small regulatory RNAs
1213 (sRNA) which in turn relieved translational repression of several virulence factors, e.g., components of the
1214 secretion system. Following ingestion by *C. elegans*, the bacteria resided inside the digestive tract of the
1215 animal where they could be activated by blue light. Doing so enhanced the bacterial pathogenicity and caused
1216 the killing of the animals. The ability to control pathogenicity of bacteria inside animals paves the way
1217 towards kinetic and mechanistic studies of the infection process (Cheng et al., 2021).

1218 Two studies explored the optogenetic manipulation of living materials consisting of *E. coli* bacteria
1219 embedded in agarose hydrogels (Sankaran et al., 2019; Sankaran and del Campo, 2019). The pDawn setup
1220 activated the expression of a red-fluorescent reporter by blue light, either leading to intracellular protein
1221 production or secretion into the extracellular space. In adapted form, this setup also enabled the light-
1222 induced production and release of deoxyviolacein (dVio) which exerts antimicrobial and antitumoral activity.
1223 To this effect, the pDawn circuit controlled the expression of the four-gene cluster *vioABCE*. Upon blue-light
1224 exposure, the living material responded by dVio release; remarkably, the embedded bacteria stayed viable
1225 and light-responsive for up to around 40 days. To facilitate light delivery *in situ*, the dVio-secreting composite
1226 hydrogels were combined with printed, biodegradable light fibers (Feng et al., 2020). This strategy enabled
1227 the optical triggering of the pDawn circuit through several centimeters of animal tissue and may benefit *in*
1228 *vivo* optogenetics in general.

1229 Light-regulated gene expression also served to control bacteria inside the digestive tract of animals.
1230 Generally, the pertinent studies leveraged optogenetics to elicit the bacterial production and secretion of
1231 substances that bestow benefits on the host. In one example, the CcaRS TCS controlled the expression of the
1232 master regulator RcsA in a *E. coli rcsA* knockout strain (Hartsough et al., 2020). Once produced under green
1233 light, RcsA activated the expression of the 19-gene *wca* operon for the synthesis and secretion of the
1234 exopolysaccharide colanic acid (CA). Notably, CA not only contributes to biofilm formation in *E. coli* and
1235 related species, but can also increase the lifespan of *C. elegans* once ingested. In the specific study, *C. elegans*
1236 worms were fed bacteria which express RcsA under the CcaRS optogenetic control. Consequently, green light
1237 promoted CA production within bacteria residing in the worm intestine and thereby granted the animals
1238 longevity. It is worth noting that constitutive CA production, for instance in a bacterial strain lacking the Lon
1239 protease, led to similar lifespan increases. Therefore, the primary utility of this captivating study is arguably
1240 to be seen in the ability to study the mechanism of the underlying microbe-animal interactions in
1241 unprecedented detail. An earlier study (Zhang and Poh, 2018) also targeted CA biosynthesis in *E. coli* by
1242 optogenetically controlling the expression of the structural gene *wcaF* within the *wca* operon. To this end,
1243 EL222 served as a transcriptional repressor and mediated the transcription in darkness of a gRNA directed
1244 against *wcaF*. In combination with dCas9, *wcaF* expression and CA production were repressed in darkness.

1245 Blue light suspended gRNA transcription and thus ramped up CA levels, in turn allowing the bacteria to form
1246 biofilms. As discussed below, biofilms also underpin the photolithographic production of structured
1247 materials.

1248 A slew of studies applied optogenetic expression control in *E. coli* BL21 and the probiotic *L. lactis* and
1249 *E. coli* Nissle 1917, with the aim of deploying these bacteria as biotherapeutic agents. Notably, both *L. lactis*
1250 and the *E. coli* Nissle strain are suitable for oral administration in microbial therapy. A pioneering report
1251 harnessed pDawn to control the expression and subsequent secretion of transforming growth factor β 1 (TGF-
1252 β 1) in *E. coli* BL21 (Yang et al., 2020). To this end, the bacteria were encapsulated and combined with
1253 upconverting nanoparticles that emit blue light upon absorption of (several quanta of) NIR light around 980
1254 nm. The UNPs thus enabled activation of the pDawn circuit in bacteria dwelling inside the colon of mice.
1255 When this setup was applied in a mouse model of the inflammatory bowel disease ulcerative colitis, the
1256 secretion of the cytokine TGF- β 1, induced by NIR light, ameliorated the symptoms of the disease. A related
1257 study (Cui et al., 2021) also investigated the use of light-responsive bacteria as biotherapeutics for the
1258 treatment of ulcerative colitis. To this end, *E. coli* Nissle bacteria expressing the cytokine interleukin 10 (IL-
1259 10) from the pDawn plasmid were applied together with UNPs. Inside the mouse intestinal tract, the bacteria
1260 were prompted by NIR light to produce and secrete IL-10. In an ulcerative colitis model, this approach
1261 reduced the adverse effects of bowel inflammation. By combining the optogenetic therapy with the optical
1262 detection of a disease biomarker (i.e. diagnostics), the study advanced a so-called optotheranostic platform.
1263 In the future, patients might use this platform to monitor themselves the disease state and progression and
1264 to then activate the optogenetic circuit for treatment as required. The earlier study also employed the pDawn
1265 circuit in *L. lactis* for the light-induced production of the cytokine interferon γ (IFN- γ) (Yang et al., 2020).
1266 Again, the bacteria were encapsulated with UNPs to enable triggering by NIR light. Optogenetically induced
1267 IFN- γ secretion in the mouse intestine slowed down progression of a mouse melanoma tumor. More recently,
1268 the *L. lactis* strain harboring the pDawn-IFN- γ circuit was used synergistically with photodynamic therapy
1269 (PDT) (Wu et al., 2022). To this end, the UNPs were first altered such that they can be excited by irradiation
1270 with 808 nm which is less strongly absorbed by tissue than 980-nm light, thus reducing potentially harmful
1271 heating. Upon illumination, one sort of UNP reacted by activating a photosensitizer which in turn generated
1272 singlet oxygen and other reactive oxygen species for PDT. Another UNP type responded with blue-light
1273 emission and thereby elicited IFN- γ secretion by the *Lactococci*. The combination of PDT, optogenetic
1274 intervention, and a drug proved most efficient for tumor therapy. The efficiency of the approach was at least
1275 partially ascribed to the synergistic activation of the immune system. Along similar lines, NIR light and UNPs
1276 activated the expression of the tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) from the EL222 circuit in *E. coli* Nissle (Pan et
1277 al., 2021). Bacteria harboring this optogenetic circuit were injected into the tail vein of mice together with
1278 the UNPs. Subsequent illumination with 980-nm light prompted TNF- α production and greatly decelerated
1279 tumor growth in a breast-cancer model.

1280 Light-responsive bacteria were also considered as potential therapeutics for other diseases and
1281 disorders. Again with the probiotic *L. lactis* as the chassis, the pDawn circuit was used to control the
1282 expression of the hormone glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) (Zhang et al., 2021). Upon oral administration,
1283 the *Lactococci* stayed viable in the rat intestinal tract for several days. Optogenetic stimulation, either via a
1284 wearable blue-light-emitting device or via UNPs and NIR light, see above, prompted GLP-1 secretion. Notably,
1285 GLP-1 enhances the glucose-dependent insulin release by the pancreatic β islet cells, among other effects. In
1286 a type-II diabetes rat model, the light-induced GLP-1 production thus lowered the blood glucose levels.
1287 Compared to constitutive expression and application of GLP-1, the optogenetically stimulated, intermittent
1288 hormone production may reduce the metabolic burden and side effects caused by GLP-1 (Zhang et al., 2021).
1289 The application of light-responsive *L. lactis* proved versatile and adaptable to other ends (Pan et al., 2022).
1290 By driving the expression of the *gadBC* genes, encoding a glutamate decarboxylase and an antiporter, from
1291 the pDawn plasmid, the production of the neurotransmitter γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) could be activated
1292 by UNPs and NIR light. In a mouse model, the light-induced GABA production by orally delivered *L. lactis*
1293 reduced anxiety-like symptoms. Moreover, the concentrations of several inflammatory factors in the brain
1294 were lowered upon optogenetic stimulation. The underlying strategy also applied to the light-induced
1295 production of the granulocyte-colony stimulating factor (GCSF) in *L. lactis* (Pan et al., 2022). In a Parkinson's
1296 disease mouse model, the light-induced GCSF production inside the gut alleviated behavioral symptoms
1297 associated with the neurological disorder. Again, the concentrations of inflammatory markers decreased
1298 upon the optogenetic intervention.

1299 These equally recent and innovative studies jointly raise the prospect of harnessing light-responsive
1300 bacteria as programmable and precisely controllable biotherapeutics. Of key importance, the optogenetic
1301 stimulation allows to modulate the response of bacteria inside the digestive tract, bloodstream, or other
1302 body compartments of animals. Notably, the relevant use cases to date mostly rely on the blue-light-sensitive
1303 pDawn and EL222 systems. Although the limited tissue penetration of blue light was overcome by using UNPs
1304 and stimulation with NIR light, this approach incurs potential disadvantages. Specifically, the resultant
1305 composite systems are more complex and employ UNPs which as non-biological entities are not genetically
1306 encodable and may prove cytotoxic. An alternative route may be the replacement of the blue-light-sensitive
1307 optogenetic implements by such that react to light of longer wavelengths, like the CcaRS TCS or the
1308 pREDusk/pREDawn circuits.

1309 Bacterial photography and structured materials

1310 Applications within this area capitalize on the spatial precision afforded by light-regulated bacterial
1311 expression, with some studies exploiting the temporal control in addition (Fig. 5C). Early on, researchers
1312 realized that optogenetically controlled expression lends itself to the generation of spatial patterns within
1313 bacterial communities and lawns. In fact, certain bacteria naturally produce spatially ordered structures

1314 when exposed to alternating dark/light cycles, e.g., (Kahl et al., 2022). As recently reviewed (Barbier et al.,
1315 2022), the patterning of microbial communities gains traction and appears suited for diverse applications in
1316 synthetic biology and biotechnology. Although not the only means of organizing bacterial populations in
1317 space, see, e.g., (Barbier et al., 2022; Chen and Wegner, 2020; Frangipane et al., 2018), light-regulated gene
1318 expression appears particularly straight-forward, versatile, and efficient.

1319 Voigt and colleagues pioneered the so-called “bacterial photography” (Levskaia et al., 2005), which
1320 has now been demonstrated for many optogenetic circuits, e.g., (Jayaraman et al., 2016; Levskaia et al.,
1321 2005; Multamäki et al., 2022; Ranzani et al., 2022; Romano et al., 2021; Ryu et al., 2010, 2014; Tabor et al.,
1322 2011). Generally, in these applications a bacterial lawn harboring a light-responsive gene expression circuit
1323 is exposed to patterned illumination. Owing to differential expression in illuminated and non-illuminated
1324 areas, spatial patterns within the bacterial lawn arise and can be visualized via suitable reporter genes, mostly
1325 fluorescent proteins but also LacZ. The spatial resolution achievable by these photolithographic approaches
1326 is principally limited by how well light can be focused and by the size and mobility of individual bacteria within
1327 the lawn. To the extent it has been tested, spatial resolution down to micrometer dimensions can be routinely
1328 achieved (Jin and Riedel-Kruse, 2018; Multamäki et al., 2022; Ohlendorf et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2018b).
1329 Beyond monochrome systems, the joint use of the Cph8:OmpR and CcaRS TCSs achieved dual-color
1330 sensitivity to red/NIR and green/red light, respectively, in *E. coli* cells (Tabor et al., 2011). This strategy was
1331 later expanded to RGB sensitivity by adding the YF1:FixJ TCS for sensing blue light (Fernandez-Rodriguez et
1332 al., 2017).

1333 In addition to spatially controlling the expression of pigments in microbial communities, patterned
1334 structures can also originate from optogenetically modulating bacterial chemotaxis. For instance, both the
1335 EL222 (Zhang et al., 2020a) and the LexRO circuits (Li et al., 2020) served to induce the expression of the
1336 bacterial chemotaxis protein CheZ under blue light. Bacteria within illuminated areas hence acquired motility
1337 but those in darkness did not. As a corollary, a net movement out of the illuminated areas resulted; put
1338 another way, the bacteria underwent negative phototaxis. A conceptually related mechanism for the
1339 phototactic movement of *E. coli* was implemented on the basis of the light-driven proton pump
1340 proteorhodopsin (Frangipane et al., 2018). Instead of light-dependent gene expression, this fascinating study
1341 relied on the light-induced generation of proton motive force across the plasma membrane which powers
1342 the bacterial flagellar motor.

1343 Biofilms are widespread among bacteria, and their formation in time and space was repeatedly
1344 subjected to optogenetic control, including by light-regulated gene expression. Two studies focused on the
1345 so-called antigen 43 (Ag43) (van der Woude and Henderson, 2008), an autotransporter protein exposed on
1346 the surface of the outer *E. coli* membrane that mediates intercell contacts and thereby promotes flocculation,
1347 aggregation, and biofilm formation (Jin and Riedel-Kruse, 2018; Nakajima et al., 2016a). Using the CcaRS TCS,

1348 Ag43 expression in *E. coli* was induced by green light and led to the aggregation and precipitation of the
1349 bacteria (Nakajima et al., 2016a). The approach may serve as a means of cell recovery in bioproduction
1350 processes. A later study subjected Ag43 expression to blue-light control using the pDawn platform (Jin and
1351 Riedel-Kruse, 2018). *E. coli* bacteria responded by biofilm formation in illuminated areas. This
1352 photolithographic strategy enabled the printing of biofilms with spatial resolution down to the micrometer
1353 range, thus much surpassing most competing methods.

1354 Precisely patterned biofilms not only benefit the study of the underlying biological processes, but also
1355 they are attractive for metabolic engineering, diagnostics, and material science. This idea is indeed borne out
1356 by a recent study that employed pDawn to photolithographically manufacture biofilms of *Shewanella*
1357 *oneidensis* (Zhao et al., 2022). These facultative anaerobic bacteria are of interest because of their capability
1358 of reducing metal ions and forming electrically conductive biofilms. To promote the formation of such films,
1359 pDawn drove the expression of different cell-surface proteins engaged in cell-cell interactions. Using the
1360 CdrAB proteins from *P. aeruginosa* to this end, the *S. oneidensis* bacteria aggregated under blue light and
1361 formed biofilms. Capitalizing on the spatial definition achieved by optogenetics, biofilms of desired extent
1362 and specifications could be produced. When inserted between two electrical leads, the biofilm acted as a
1363 living electrode material and conducted current. The electrochemical properties of the biofilm could be easily
1364 tuned by varying the illumination pattern and duration. An earlier study (Hu et al., 2017) optogenetically
1365 drove biofilm formation in *S. oneidensis* as well but used the c-di-GMP-producing BphS to this end. NIR light
1366 thus promoted bacterial deposition on an electrode, with scope for potential applications in microbial fuel
1367 cells. BphS also enabled the NIR-light-induced formation of *E. coli* biofilms for use as living biocatalysts (Hu
1368 et al., 2019). As demonstrated for the conversion of tryptophan into indole within such biofilms, this strategy
1369 may apply to bioproduction processes. BphS was further employed for optogenetically modulating biofilms
1370 of the opportunistic pathogen *P. aeruginosa* (Huang et al., 2018). To precisely regulate intracellular c-di-GMP
1371 levels, BphS was combined with BlrP1 from *K. pneumoniae* which serves as a blue-light-activated EAL
1372 phosphodiesterase that degrades this second messenger. Elevated c-di-GMP prompted the expression of
1373 several target genes, including *cdrAB*, see above, and thus resulted in biofilm formation. The bimodal
1374 regulation by blue and NIR light yielded precisely structured biofilms, well suited to analyzing the transition
1375 between planktonic and sessile lifestyles that contributes to the *P. aeruginosa* virulence. In a related
1376 approach, the pDawn circuit mediated the expression of a constitutively active EAL enzyme in *P. aeruginosa*
1377 (Pu et al., 2018). Within bacteria exposed to blue light, intracellular c-di-GMP was thus depleted and biofilm
1378 formation reduced. Finally, EL222 was used to control the *wgaAB* genes in a corresponding *S. meliloti*
1379 knockout strain (Pirhanov et al., 2021). Blue light prompted gene expression and thereby activated the
1380 biosynthesis of exopolysaccharides which promoted cell aggregation and biofilm formation. *S. meliloti*
1381 biofilms of varying extent, thickness, and properties were thus obtained and can be prospectively used for
1382 the analysis of plant-rhizobium interactions.

1383 The above use cases compellingly illustrate how light-regulated gene expression can establish spatial
1384 patterns in bacterial communities. Beyond their utility in basic research, these approaches garner interest
1385 for the production of structured materials, as already hinted at in certain of the above examples (Zhao et al.,
1386 2022) (Fig. 5C). Several studies employed the CsgA protein which upon secretion forms so-called curli fibrils
1387 on the bacterial cell surface and mediates biofilm formation (Chen et al., 2014). Importantly, CsgA can
1388 accommodate guest peptides and proteins which are thereby displayed on the bacterial outside in high copy
1389 number. Via the pDawn circuit, the expression of polyhistidine-tagged CsgA was spatially controlled by blue
1390 light down to a resolution of around 100 μm (Wang et al., 2018b). Within the illuminated areas, *E. coli*
1391 bacteria thus assembled into biofilms decorated with polyhistidine moieties that can enter metal
1392 coordination bonds with certain divalent cations. Using this strategy, diverse nanoobjects linked to
1393 nitriloacetic acid tags could be assembled on the biofilm with precise spatial control. Given its modularity,
1394 this strategy proved versatile and suitable for different applications. In addition to labeling with fluorescent
1395 probes, the light-responsive biofilms could also direct the spatial assembly of gold nanoparticles which upon
1396 further derivatization conducted electrical current. Taken together, the light-controlled, programmable
1397 assembly of various nanoobjects empowers the hierarchical construction of two- and three-dimensional
1398 materials. The principal concept extended to the multimodal optogenetic expression of several CsgA variants
1399 bearing different tags (Moser et al., 2019). Based on a previously constructed *E. coli* strain with RGB sensitivity
1400 (Fernandez-Rodriguez et al., 2017), the formation and surface properties of biofilms, as well as the protein
1401 expression within the constituent bacteria, could be spatially controlled by different light colors. This
1402 platform enabled the photolithographic printing of biofilm patterns on several materials, including glass and
1403 textiles.

1404 Bacteria that light-dependently express CsgA derivatives were also deployed as living glue systems (An
1405 et al., 2020). To this end, the CsgA protein was fused to the Mfp3s peptide which derives from the foot protein
1406 of mussels and mediates attachment to solid support. Compared to CsgA alone, expression of the CsgA-
1407 Mfp3s protein resulted in stronger adhesion of the bacterial biofilms. The adhesive properties were further
1408 increased by including a tyrosinase in the system which catalyzed the oxidation of tyrosine to *ortho*-
1409 dihydroxyphenylalanine within the Mfp3s domain. The biofilm could furthermore capture polystyrene
1410 microspheres which became entangled within the curli fibrils and formed a strong composite. Light-activated
1411 CsgA-Mfp3s expression from the pDawn circuit thus enabled the localized formation of hybrid materials
1412 which could serve as glue to repair defects in other materials. This concept was later extended by mineralizing
1413 the biofilms with calcium phosphate (Wang et al., 2021). The Mfp3s protein, spread out along the curli fibrils,
1414 nucleated the deposition of the salt as hydroxyapatite on the biofilm. By applying different blue-light regimes,
1415 the resulting composite material could be adjusted in its spatial extent, thickness, and mechanical properties.
1416 Combined with the above microspheres, the living biomaterial formed an even stronger material, designated
1417 cement, that again served to repair lesions in materials on demand.

1418 Perspectives

1419 Following in the footsteps of the first setup for the light-dependent control of bacterial gene expression
1420 (Levskaya et al., 2005), numerous optogenetic strategies have been added over the past two decades (see
1421 Table 1). As detailed in this article, the presently available repertoire covers the entire near-UV to NIR portion
1422 of the electromagnetic spectrum (see Fig. 1B). Although mostly based on the regulation of transcription
1423 initiation and elongation, several of these systems unlock additional footholds for the optogenetic expression
1424 control, e.g., by acting at the levels of recombination or translation (see Fig. 3 and 4). After their initial
1425 description and proof-of-principle demonstration, at least certain of the available optogenetic tools have
1426 stood the test of practice, as they have been adopted for synthetic biology, bioproduction, and theranostics.
1427 By capitalizing on the advantages of optogenetics, i.e. genetic encoding, spatiotemporal precision,
1428 reversibility, and non-invasiveness, novel applications arose that were previously impossible or even
1429 inconceivable (see Fig. 5). At the time of writing, the setups based on EL222 (Jayaraman et al., 2016; Motta-
1430 Mena et al., 2014), CcaRS (Tabor et al., 2011), and YF1:FixJ (Möglich et al., 2009; Ohlendorf et al., 2012) are
1431 the most widely deployed (see Fig. 4B, C). In part, this predominance likely owes to legacy, that is, the early
1432 implementation of these system. That notwithstanding, numerous examples bridging multiple application
1433 areas and bacterial species suggest that these setups offer particularly robust and stringent optogenetic
1434 responses in diverse settings.

1435 The flurry of new optogenetic tools released over just the past two years, e.g., (Dietler et al., 2021;
1436 Lalwani et al., 2021a; Li et al., 2020; Multamäki et al., 2022; Ranzani et al., 2022; Romano et al., 2021; Sheets
1437 et al., 2020), is testament to the increasing relevance of light-controlled bacterial expression for basic and
1438 applied research. With each new setup, key questions beg: Are the already available tools limiting, and if so,
1439 how and when? How should and how can they be improved? Which tools are currently lacking for controlling
1440 bacterial expression? Although answering these questions universally (and, without bias) is challenging,
1441 several trends emerge. First, for at least some of the existing optogenetic implements, there seems to be
1442 scope for improvement of, for instance, basal activity, dynamic range, and sensitivity. As admirably
1443 demonstrated for the CcaRS TCS (Ong and Tabor, 2018), the unrelenting optimization of the photoreceptor
1444 itself and downstream circuitry can greatly boost these parameters. Second, not least given the equally
1445 promising and exciting applications of light-regulated bacterial gene expression for theranostics, there
1446 appears to be unmet demand for optogenetic circuits that sensitively react to light of long wavelengths,
1447 preferably within the so-called NIR transparent window (Weissleder, 2001). Third, notwithstanding the
1448 diversity and ingenuity of the arsenal for optogenetic control of bacterial expression, room may exist for
1449 additional implements, for instance (d)Cas9 variants that would enable the efficient regulation by light of
1450 endogenous genes encoded on the bacterial chromosome. Similarly, members of the Cas family, such as
1451 Cas13 which targets RNA molecules (Abudayyeh et al., 2016), have not been explored for light control so far,

1452 but could unlock new directions for the optogenetic control in bacteria and beyond. Future design efforts
1453 along all three lines will doubtless benefit from the inherent modularity of many optogenetic circuits. This is
1454 equally true for light-responsive TCSs, e.g., (Levskaya et al., 2005; Möglich et al., 2009; Multamäki et al., 2022;
1455 Ong and Tabor, 2018), and oligomerization-based setups, e.g., (Chen et al., 2016; Dietler et al., 2021;
1456 Kaberniuk et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020; Romano et al., 2021), either of which can be altered by substituting one
1457 photosensor module for another. The latter category stands to benefit from years of basic research and
1458 genome mining that provided diverse photoreceptor pairs that associate or dissociate upon light exposure
1459 (Guntas et al., 2015; Kuwasaki et al., 2022; Redchuk et al., 2017; Strauss et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2016).
1460 Promisingly, recent reports demonstrated the functional expression of plant phytochromes (Raghavan et al.,
1461 2020) and cryptochromes (McQuillen et al., 2022) in *E. coli*, thus raising the prospect of bacterial use of these
1462 photoreceptors which underpin manifold and highly stringent optogenetic systems in mammalian cells.
1463 Furthermore, mechanistic studies provided insights on key residues and structural features which determine
1464 the kinetics (Kawano et al., 2013; Pudasaini et al., 2015), direction (Möglich et al., 2009; Nakajima et al.,
1465 2016b; Ohlendorf et al., 2012), and dynamic range (Dietler et al., 2021; Gourinchas et al., 2019; Strickland et
1466 al., 2010) of photoswitching, thereby facilitating the rational design of photoreceptors and optogenetic
1467 circuits with tailored functionality. Libraries of systematically or randomly constructed receptor and circuit
1468 variants can be combed by high-throughput screening based on fluorescence signals. Such approaches can
1469 complement rational design strategies, especially for complex engineering challenges or when the
1470 mechanistic understanding of the target system is limited.

1471 In pursuit of optogenetic control in deep biological tissue, several strategies aim at using red or NIR
1472 light to excite photoreceptors. Although residue exchanges around the chromophore could in principle
1473 induce a red-shift of absorbance spectra, such efforts had only modest success in flavin-based
1474 photoreceptors, arguably owing to the rigid scaffold of the isoalloxazine heterocycle (Goncharov et al., 2021;
1475 Röllen et al., 2021). By contrast, the color diversity realized across CBCRs and certain algal phytochromes
1476 (Fushimi and Narikawa, 2019; Rockwell et al., 2014) suggests that the chromophore and its absorbance
1477 spectrum are more malleable in the phytochrome superfamily. Alternatively, the original chromophore can
1478 be substituted for red-shifted versions, provided the bacteria can import or produce the heterologous
1479 chromophores (Mathes et al., 2009). However, the incorporation of heterologous chromophores without
1480 compromising photochemistry and signal transduction remains a major challenge (Mathes et al., 2009).
1481 While point mutations around the chromophore were extensively explored in nature and the lab to create
1482 red-shifted channelrhodopsins (Klapoetke et al., 2014), for the optogenetic control of bacterial gene
1483 expression the replacement of photosensors for red-light sensitive versions, i.e. members of the the
1484 phytochrome family, turned out to be the more successful strategy (Kaberniuk et al., 2021; Multamäki et al.,
1485 2022). Short of photosensor substitution, excitation at double or triple the original wavelength can be
1486 achieved by multiple-photon stimulation. Although widely applied in channelrhodopsins (Rickgauer and

1487 Tank, 2009), two-photon excitation has to date not seen much use in bacterial optogenetics. Two-photon
1488 excitation is principally feasible for at least certain soluble photoreceptor classes (Homans et al., 2018;
1489 Piatkevich et al., 2017; Sokolovski et al., 2021), but may suffer from low two-photon absorption cross sections
1490 (Kinjo et al., 2019). Nanotechnology offers an alternative approach that generates visible excitation light in
1491 deep tissue. For instance, UNPs convert NIR light into shorter wavelengths that in turn activate optogenetic
1492 circuits (Chen et al., 2018; Hososhima et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2020). In bigger specimens such as humans or
1493 for transcranial stimulation through bone, NIR excitation is still limited to shallow tissue regions. Though not
1494 yet applied to bacterial optogenetics, an interesting alternative may be provided by a different type of
1495 nanoparticles which can be charged by irradiation with UV light (Wu et al., 2019). Subsequent stimulation of
1496 such mechanoluminescent particles with focused ultrasound prompts the emission of light around 470 nm
1497 which can be harvested for eliciting optogenetic responses. Employing this sono-optogenetic strategy, the
1498 particles may first be charged outside of the animal body or near its surface before circulating in the
1499 bloodstream to the desired site. Triggering of the optogenetic circuit is then accomplished via application of
1500 ultrasound which penetrates biological tissue readily.

1501 On the whole, light-regulated bacterial expression has undergone a rapid transformation over the past
1502 twenty years, in terms of both the optogenetic tools and applications at hand. The use cases realized to date
1503 incontrovertibly demonstrate the principal feasibility, versatility, and utility of bacterial expression control
1504 by optogenetics. Moreover, they are bound to spark additional applications along similar but hopefully also
1505 unrelated lines. Researchers pursuing such efforts can choose from and adapt a wide repertoire of options;
1506 we hope that the current survey informs this choice.

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2080 Figures

2081 Figure 1

2082 Light-regulated gene expression in bacteria. (A) The schematic depicts the basic principles of the optogenetic
2083 regulation of bacterial gene expression. Sensory photoreceptors harbor chromophores that undergo
2084 photochemical reactions in response to light absorption. The photochemical level is coupled to allosteric
2085 transitions within the protein moiety that culminate in altered photoreceptor activity. In turn, the light-
2086 induced activity change prompts the bacterial expression of the protein of interest. As illustrated in the
2087 scheme, certain photoreceptors are photochromic and can be bidirectionally toggled by two light colors. (B)
2088 Representative absorbance spectra of select sensory photoreceptors, with light-oxygen-voltage (LOV) and
2089 BLUF receptors shown in blue, the paradigm cyanobacteriochrome (CBCR) CcaS in green (Pg state) and red
2090 (Pr state), and bacterial phytochromes (BphP) in pink (Pr state) and brown (Pfr state). The spectra are scaled
2091 to reflect the individual peak extinction coefficients, i.e. around $12,500 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $30,000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $90,000$
2092 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for LOV/BLUF, CBCR (Pg), and BphP (Pr), respectively. (C) Simplified photochemistry of LOV
2093 receptors. Upon absorption of blue light by the dark-adapted state D_{450} , a covalent adduct forms between
2094 atom C4a of the flavin chromophore and the S_{γ} atom of a conserved cysteine residue. The resultant
2095 protonation of the N5 atom within the signaling state S_{390} is read out by a conserved glutamine residue which
2096 undergoes a sidechain flip in response. The signaling state passively decays to the dark-adapted resting state.
2097 (D) Simplified photochemistry of BphPs. A biliverdin (BV) chromophore (pyrrole rings marked A through D) is
2098 covalently linked to a cysteine residue. Within the Pr state, the C15=C16 double bond adopts the 15Z
2099 configuration. Upon absorption of red light, this bond isomerizes to the 15E state, thus giving rise to the Pfr
2100 state. Absorption of far-red light drives the reversion to the Pr state. Conventional BphPs exhibit the Pr form
2101 as their dark-adapted state, as opposed to bathyphytochromes which feature the Pfr state in darkness.
2102 Although cyanobacterial phytochromes and CBCRs employ the reduced bilin chromophore phycocyanobilin
2103 instead of BV, the principal photochemistry hinging on 15Z/15E isomerization is shared by these receptors,
2104 too. CBCRs diversify this fundamental photochemical response to achieve sensitivity to light bands other than
2105 red and far-red (Fushimi and Narikawa, 2019).

2106 Figure 2

2107 Principles of optogenetic control. (A) Sensory photoreceptors and genetic circuits for the light-regulated gene
2108 expression in bacteria are characterized by key performance parameters. If all photoreceptor molecules
2109 dwell in their low-activity state, the circuit generates a basal output, also denoted as leak activity. Once all
2110 photoreceptors are converted to their more active state, maximal activity is generated by the circuit. The
2111 ratio of maximal over basal activity is referred to as the dynamic range or regulatory efficiency/factor.
2112 Optogenetic circuits differ in their light sensitivity, commonly reported as the light dose required for half-

2113 maximal activation, and the cooperativity of their response to illumination. The solid curve shows the
2114 response of a non-cooperative optogenetic circuit where I_{50} is the light dose at which half-maximal activation
2115 occurs. By contrast, the dashed and dotted curves denote circuits that respond to light cooperatively with
2116 Hill coefficients of 2 and 4, respectively. (B) Many optogenetic tools for controlling bacterial gene expression
2117 rely on light-dependent dimerization equilibria. Associating photoreceptors exhibit a lower dissociation
2118 constant under blue light ($K_D = 0.1$, blue curve) than in darkness ($K_D = 10$, black), thus causing their activation
2119 profiles to be displaced along the concentration axis. The dashed line denotes the difference of the dimeric
2120 receptor fraction in light and darkness for the assumed scenario of a 100-fold changed dissociation constant
2121 (left scale). The dotted line plots the ratio of the dimer fractions (right scale). (C) Photoreceptors can
2122 substantially differ in their dark-recovery kinetics, and for certain classes deliberate residue substitutions
2123 near the chromophore modulate these kinetics. After initial stimulation by light (blue bar), a given
2124 photoreceptor and hence its activity recover with its intrinsic rate constant. The dashed red curve simulates
2125 a receptor that recovers at a tenth of the rate of that for the blue curve. The dashed black line denotes the
2126 time point at which the blue and red curves have the maximal difference. (D) As in panel C but for a dimeric
2127 photoreceptor which is assumed to be active if at least one of its subunits dwells in the light-adapted state.
2128 After illumination ceases, the recovery of activity is hence sigmoidal rather than exponential. As a corollary,
2129 the maximal difference between the two simulated photoreceptors which differ in their dark-recovery rates
2130 by a factor of 10 is larger than in scenario C (dashed black line). (E) Certain photoreceptor circuits are sensitive
2131 to a second stimulus, e.g., light of a different color, a chemical inducer, or changes in temperature (Dietler et
2132 al., 2021; Romano et al., 2021). Initial photostimulation (red bar) can be counteracted by subsequent
2133 application of the second signal (brown bar). (F) Photochromic photoreceptors, e.g., phytochromes, can be
2134 reversibly and repeatedly toggled between their dark-adapted and light-adapted states by two colors of light.
2135 These photoreceptors thus constitute a special case of scenario E. Following initial photostimulation (red
2136 bar), the system can either recover in darkness (blue curve) or be actively returned to the initial state by
2137 illumination at desired times (brown bar, red dashed curve). All simulations were conducted with Fit-o-mat
2138 (Möglich, 2018).

2139 Figure 3

2140 Existing and potential toeholds for the optogenetic control of bacterial gene expression. Expression requires
2141 a DNA template encoding an intact transcriptional unit, and the provision of this unit can be modulated by
2142 recombination events (mechanism **①**) (Sheets et al., 2020). Alternatively, the assembly of a functional RNA
2143 polymerase (RNAP) holoenzyme can be modulated (**②**), for example by controlling the association of the
2144 endogenous core polymerase ($\alpha_2\beta\beta'$) with its σ factor, or by reconstitution of a split viral polymerase
2145 (Baumschlager et al., 2017; Han et al., 2017). The main checkpoint for transcription is initiation, which is
2146 promoted by activator proteins, often via productive interactions with the C-terminal domain of the RNAP α

2147 subunits (α -CTD), and hindered by repressors (3, 4). Prokaryotic activators and repressors are usually
2148 homodimeric, and their activity can hence be governed by controlling their assembly by light, either directly,
2149 e.g., in case of EL222 (Nash et al., 2011), or indirectly in case of the widespread two-component systems
2150 (Levskaya et al., 2005; Möglich et al., 2009; Tabor et al., 2011). At the mRNA level, expression control can be
2151 accomplished by directing RNA-binding proteins, e.g., PAL (Weber et al., 2019), to the 5'- and 3'-untranslated
2152 regions (UTR) of the transcript (5). Binding to the 5'-UTR may mask the ribosome-binding site (or, Shine-
2153 Dalgarno [SD] sequence) and thereby interfere with translation initiation (Ranzani et al., 2022). Alternatively,
2154 binding to the 3'-UTR could be harnessed for regulating intracellular RNA stability (Tang and Guest, 1999).
2155 Post expression, target proteins can be controlled by binding to other proteins or sequestration into protein
2156 clusters, which may incur activity modulation (6), or by governing their intracellular lifetime and eventual
2157 degradation (7). Beyond the generic strategies in the schematic, numerous proteins were also subjected to
2158 light-dependent allosteric control via direct fusion with a photoreceptor unit.

2159 Figure 4

2160 Select principal strategies for the light-dependent control of gene expression. (A) The phage-derived T7
2161 polymerase can be dissected into two parts which in separation have little activity. By fusing the polymerase
2162 fragments to photoassociating LOV domains, such as the Magnets (Kawano et al., 2015), T7 can be
2163 reconstituted under blue light, and transcription ensues (Baumschlager et al., 2017; Han et al., 2017). (B) A
2164 group of strategies exploit the homodimeric nature of bacterial activator and repressor proteins. Via
2165 truncation, dimerization can be impaired, thus rendering monomers with little DNA affinity, let alone
2166 regulatory effects. As in strategy A, linkage to photoassociating LOV modules, such as *N. crassa* Vivid (*NcVVD*)
2167 (Zoltowski and Crane, 2008), allows dimerization and activity to be regained upon blue-light exposure. For
2168 instance, the widely used AraC transcriptional activator was subjected to light control thus (Romano et al.,
2169 2021). In a similar vein, repressor proteins such as LexA (Li et al., 2020) or TetR (Dietler et al., 2021) can be
2170 monomerized through truncation and linked to the photodissociating *R. sphaeroides* LOV domain (*RsLOV*)
2171 (Conrad et al., 2013). Light exposure leads to a dissociation of the LOV-linked repressor and hence to
2172 transcriptional activation. (C) A large group of studies (Levskaya et al., 2005; Ohlendorf et al., 2012; Tabor et
2173 al., 2011) employ two-component systems, consisting in their canonical form of a sensor histidine kinase
2174 (SHK) and a response regulator (RR). Depending on illumination, photoresponsive SHKs adopt kinase-active
2175 or phosphatase-active states (Möglich, 2019), thus promoting RR phosphorylation and dephosphorylation,
2176 respectively. Once phosphorylated, the RR serves as a transcriptional activator at target promoters. As
2177 depicted in the scheme, certain SHKs act as net kinases in their dark-adapted states before being converted
2178 to their phosphatase-active states by light (Levskaya et al., 2005; Möglich et al., 2009), while other SHKs are
2179 phosphatase-active in darkness and become kinase-active under light (Tabor et al., 2011). (D) Several
2180 optogenetic strategies are based on cyclic-nucleotide second messengers, in particular 3', 5'-cyclic adenosine

2181 monophosphate and, as shown in the scheme, 3', 5'-cyclic-diguanylate (c-di-GMP). Activated by light,
2182 diguanylate cyclases (GGDEF) catalyze the formation of c-di-GMP which binds and thereby activates specific
2183 transcriptional activators (Ryu and Gomelsky, 2014). The hydrolysis of c-di-GMP is mediated by EAL
2184 phosphodiesterases, certain of which are also responsive to light (Huang et al., 2018). (E) The LOV receptor
2185 *NmPAL* from *N. multipartita* binds specific RNA sequences upon blue-light activation. Once embedded
2186 adjacent to the Shine-Dalgarno sequence (SD) of target mRNAs, light-induced PAL binding to these sequences
2187 interferes with ribosome binding and reduces expression (Ranzani et al., 2022; Weber et al., 2019).

2188 Figure 5

2189 Use cases of optogenetic expression control in bacteria. (A) Light-dependent gene expression underpins the
2190 regulation and optimization of bioproduction processes. The dynamic control afforded by optogenetics for
2191 instance allows the separation in time of growth and production phases. In a two-stage fermentation process,
2192 biomass can be first accumulated before illumination starts and production ramps up (Montaño López et al.,
2193 2022). The fundamental approach extends to systems that respond to several light colors to for example turn
2194 on and off the expression of target genes on demand. Optogenetic actuation may be combined with online
2195 (optical) monitoring of the system state, thus allowing continuous feedback control of the system (Miliás-
2196 Argeitis et al., 2016). (B) Optogenetics serves to control by light gene expression in bacteria residing inside
2197 the body of animals, e.g., within the intestinal tract. This strategy for example enables the optogenetic
2198 stimulation of the bacterial production and secretion of choice hormones or chemicals that bestow health
2199 benefits on the animal host (Hartsough et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020). (C) Owing to the spatial precision of
2200 optogenetics, light-regulated bacterial expression lends itself to the production of structured biomaterials.
2201 The pertinent studies commonly expose lawns of bacteria to patterned illumination which elicits the spatially
2202 confined expression of target genes. Beyond enabling the so-called “bacterial photography” (Levskaya et al.,
2203 2005), the concept can be adapted for material production. For instance, light can prompt the bacteria to
2204 form biofilms which can be mineralized with inorganic compounds to thus yield composite living materials
2205 (Wang et al., 2021).

2206 Tables

2207 Table 1 - Strategies for light-regulated gene expression in bacteria.

Name	Photoreceptor mechanism	Target process and mechanism	Dynamic range ^a	Chromophore / color sensitivity	References
Opto-Cre-Vvd (split Cre-NcVVD/Magnets)	split protein, dimerization	recombination	+12 × (estimated from figure) ^b	FMN / blue	(Sheets et al., 2020)
Opto-Flp-Vvd (split Flp-NcVVD/Magnets)	split protein, dimerization	recombination	+6 × (estimated from figure)	FMN / blue	(Sheets et al., 2020)
OptoT7 (split T7, Magnets)	split protein, dimerization	polymerase reconstitution	+332 ×	FMN / blue	(Baumschlager et al., 2017)
split T7-NcVVD/Magnets	split protein, dimerization, allostery	polymerase reconstitution and activity	+50-100 × (estimated from figure)	FMN / blue	(Han et al., 2017)
split T7-AtPhyB:PIF3	split protein, dimerization, intein processing	polymerase reconstitution	+5 × (lycopene production)	PCB / red and far-red	(Raghavan et al., 2020)
Cph8:OmpR	TCS	transcriptional activation	-9 × -72 ×	PCB / red and far-red	(Levskaya et al., 2005) (Schmidl et al., 2014)

pDusk (YF1:FixJ) pDawn	TCS + λ cl repressor	transcriptional activation (plus inverter)	-15 \times +460 \times	FMN / blue	(Ohlendorf et al., 2012)
OptoLAC (YF1:FixJ)	TCS, λ cl and lacI repressors	transcriptional activation (plus inverter)	-61 \times	FMN / blue	(Lalwani et al., 2021a)
YGS24:GacA	TCS	transcriptional activation	+10 \times	FMN / blue	(Cheng et al., 2021)
CcaS:CcaR	TCS	transcriptional activation	+6 \times +117 \times +593 \times	PCB / red and green	(Tabor et al., 2011) (Schmidl et al., 2014) (Ong and Tabor, 2018)
UirS:UirR	TCS	transcriptional activation	+6 \times	PCB / UV-violet and green	(Ramakrishnan and Tabor, 2016)
pREDusk (<i>DrF1</i> :FixJ) pREDawn	TCS + λ cl repressor	transcriptional activation (plus inverter)	-200 \times +70 \times	BV / red and far-red	(Multamäki et al., 2022)
BphP1:PpsR2	heterodimerization, allostery	transcriptional repression	+2.5 \times	BV / red and far-red	(Ong et al., 2018)

LOV-TAP (AsLOV2-TrpR)	allostery	transcriptional repression	n.d.	FMN / blue	(Strickland et al., 2008, 2010)
LightOff (LexA- <i>NcVVD</i>) LEVion	dimerization + λ cl repressor	transcriptional repression (plus inverter)	-10,000 \times +1,000 \times	FMN / blue	(Chen et al., 2016)
LexRO (LexA ₄₀₈ - <i>RsLOV</i>)	dimer dissociation	transcriptional repression	+500 \times	FMN / blue	(Li et al., 2020)
iLight (LexA ₄₀₈ - <i>/sPad_PCM</i>)	dimer-tetramer association	transcriptional repression	-115 \times	BV / red and far-red	(Kaberniuk et al., 2021)
pLITR (TetR- <i>RsLOV</i>) pLATR (TetR- <i>NcVVD</i> , TetR- <i>Ptaur</i>)	dimerization dimer dissociation	transcriptional repression	+14 \times -75 \times	FMN / blue	(Dietler et al., 2021)
TRU (TetR- <i>NcVVD</i>) TAU	split protein, dimerization + lacI repressor	transcriptional repression (plus inverter)	-13 \times +5 \times	FMN / blue	(Komera et al., 2022)
CarH	allostery, tetramerization	transcriptional repression	+10 \times (LacZ reporter in <i>Myxococcus xanthus</i>)	B ₁₂ / green	(Ortiz-Guerrero et al., 2011)

pBLind	dimerization, allostery	transcriptional activation	+5 ×	FMN / blue	(Jayaraman et al., 2016)
pBLrep			-3 ×		(Ding et al., 2020)
BLAT (EL222)			+24 ×		
BLRT (EL222)			-53 ×		
pEL EL222			-5 ×		
BLADE (NcVVD-AraC, AraC-VfLOV)	dimerization	transcriptional activation	+15 ×	FMN / blue	(Romano et al., 2021)
bPAC	cAMP second messenger + CAP	transcriptional activation	+300 × (cAMP production)	FAD / blue	(Ryu et al., 2010; Stierl et al., 2011)
IlaC	cAMP second messenger + CAP	transcriptional activation	+6 × (cAMP production)	BV / red and far-red	(Ryu et al., 2014)
PaaC			+4 ×		(Ettl et al., 2018)
DdPAC			+7 ×		(Stüven et al., 2019)
mPAC	cAMP second messenger + CAP	transcriptional activation	+30 × (cAMP production)	FMN / blue	(Raffelberg et al., 2013)
cPAC	cAMP second messenger + CAP	transcriptional activation	+3 × (cAMP production)	PCB / blue and green	(Blain-Hartung et al., 2018)

AnPixJg2-AC	cAMP second messenger + CAP	transcriptional activation	+2-3 × (cAMP production)	PCB / red and green	(Fushimi et al., 2017)
PaaG	cGMP second messenger	transcriptional activation	+14 × (cGMP production)	BV / red and far-red	(Ettl et al., 2018)
BphS	c-di-GMP second messenger + MrkH	transcriptional activation	+40 × (LacZ)	BV / red and far-red	(Ryu and Gomelsky, 2014)
pCrepusculo (<i>NmPAL</i>) pAurora	allostery + λ cl repressor	translational repression	-10 × +67 ×	FMN / blue	(Ranzani et al., 2022; Weber et al., 2019)
LicV (LicT- <i>NcVVD</i>)	dimerization	transcriptional termination	+17 ×	FMN / blue	(Liu et al., 2022)
PRU (TEV protease- <i>NcVVD</i>) PAU	split protein, dimerization + cleavable LAA tag	protein degradation	-12 × +4 ×	FMN / blue	(Komera et al., 2022)

2208 ^a: Unless stated otherwise, the listed dynamic ranges are based on the expression of fluorescent reporter genes.

2209 ^b: Positive factors denote an induction of gene expression by light, whereas negative factors signify a reduction of expression under light.

(A) Opto-T7

(B) Activator/Repressor dimerization

(C) Two-component systems

(E) Optribogenetics

(D) Second messengers

